

NOTES ON THE MANUFACTURE, COLOURS, AND BIOGRAPHY OF CODEx LAUD

Mexican Pictorial Manuscript at the Bodleian Library, University of Oxford

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PRELIMINARY WORDS

This document reports on the results of a codicological study on the original Codex Laud. This macroscopical, non-intrusive work was carried out from the 3rd to the 5th of February, 2020, in the conservation studio at the Weston Library of the Bodleian Library, Oxford. I especially thank all those involved in granting me permission to work at the Weston Library; in particular, Virginia Lladó Buisán, Head of Conservation and Collection Care at the Bodleian Libraries, Martin Kauffman, Head of Early and Rare Collections in the Special Collections, and Robert Minte, Senior Conservator and Collection Care. We owe a debt of gratitude to Robert for his patience towards us and his great care in handling, opening, and carefully placing the codex so that Prof. Dr. Katarzyna Mikulska and I could observe it. I am grateful to her for teaching me the steps to study the material conditions of this unique and extraordinary manuscript. All photos on this report were taken by her, unless stated otherwise.

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INTRODUCTION

Codex Laud is one of the manuscripts of the so-called Borgia Group. This group of eight codices was presumably created close to the arrival of the Spanish in Mesoamerica, and is grouped together based on three factors: their prehispanic pictorial style, their material composition of animal skin (except for one, made of paper), and their calendrical, divinatory and ritual content. The names of these codices are Borgia, Vaticanus B, Cospi, Fejérváry-Mayer, Tututepetongo (or Porfirio Díaz, only the reverse), Fonds Mexicain 20, and one page recently found in San Bartolo Yautepec (Jansen and Pérez Jiménez 2004; Boone 2007; Urcid and Doesburg 2016). After more than one hundred years of study, we have come to the conclusion that these books were used as manuals for rituals, medicine, and prognostications (Nowotny 1961; Anders et al. 1993; Mikulska 2008; Rojas 2016). According to the colonial chronicles of Central Mexico, they were the *tonalamatl* – or “books of the days” – used by the *tonalpouhque*, the priests who were the contemporary specialists on matters concerning the calendar, its auguries, and prescriptions (Sahagún 1577:246v).

Codex Laud is one of the less studied codices of the Borgia group. In terms of interpretation of the painting-writing of Codex Laud, the most extensive research has been carried out by Nowotny (1961) and Ferdinand Anders and Maarten Jansen (1994). In regards to codicological analysis – that is, the study of the materials, manufacture techniques, and pigments – there have been more investigations, beginning with Cottie Burland (1966) and recently by Ludo Snijders (2014), María Isabel Álvarez Icaza (2014, 2019; with Dupey 2018) and Davide Domenici with the MOLAB team (2019; Domenici et al. 2017; Grazia et al. 2019; Buti et al. 2014). Other works of partial and general interpretations can be found in Lord Kingsborough (1831), Francisco del Paso y Troncoso (1961), Eduard Seler (1900, 1902-1923), Walter Lehman (1905), José Alcina Franch (1955), Carlos Martínez Marín (1961), Karl Nowotny (1961), Luis Corona Núñez (1964), Thomas Barthel (1972, 1973, 1975, 1981), Virginia Ehrman Dahlin (1981), Laura Lewis (1996, 1997), and Elizabeth Boone (2006, 2007).

Codex Laud formed part of the great collection of rare books and antiquities of William Laud (1573-1645), former Archbishop of Canterbury and Chancellor of Oxford University. He acquired the Mexican codex during the 1630s under unknown circumstances and from an unknown seller. Between 1635 and 1639, and after being named chancellor of the university, Laud began to donate books to the library, among them, Codex Laud. Unfortunately, we lack any further information about how this particular *tonalamatl* reached Europe.

About this report

The aim of this codicological analysis of Codex Laud was to macroscopically observe the materials of support, manufacture techniques, and pigments of Codex Laud. This analysis was different from previous codicological and macroscopical analysis on this codex (namely, Álvarez Icaza 2014; Grazia et al. 2019; Domenici et al. 2019; Buti et al. 2014), since it attempted to complement the observed data on materials, stylistic traits, and colours with information about the symbolic content depicted on the images and chapters. In other words, by observing certain physical features of the codex, I attempt to add knowledge and answer particular questions about the symbolisms associated with the religious and divinatory purposes of different chapters as well as the book as a whole. With the new data recovered, I expect to bring forward ideas on the technical and intellectual (perhaps even cognitive) skills of the person(s) who fabricated, painted, used, and read the book. This new data will be part of my current work on the interpretation of Codex Laud.

To be concrete, the aims while observing the codex were:

1. To understand the manufacturing technique of the codex, including the way of joining the leather strips and covers, repairs or reinforcement of unions, as well as the application of gypsum and pigments and the writing-painting process, together with the identification of sketches or guides of some kind;
2. To identify the palette of colours used and variation of hues as well as pictorial styles within the codex (different hands? different moments?), including possible errors, amendments or palimpsests, and traces of paint-transfers;
3. To acquire any other data that may add to the biography of the codex and help us to comprehend the symbolism of its scenes or solve some previous assumptions on this manuscript .

Below, I structure the findings for this report by following a series of questions, which were originally raised in my proposal to the Bodleian Library. Hence, instead of presenting physical details page by page, I present the results in the form of answers to a series of questions. These questions go hand to hand to issues and interpretations of the codex previously suggested by scholars. I end by considering some new data, which opens up the possibility of knowing from whom and where the codex had been acquired.

IS CODEX LAUD MISSING PAGES?

The idea that Codex Laud is missing pages began with Burland (1966) and was also developed by Jansen (Anders y Jansen 1994). It is mainly based on the analysis of the symbolic content of the scenes on the end pages of the codex, which present apparently incomplete calendrical sequences. Boone (2006) contested these observations and through a visual analysis she offered arguments against this idea. Furthermore, she supported the codicological information given by Burland himself. Burland (1966) observed in the codex that the thicker and harder leather covers are very well glued to the ends of the codex, so according to his ideas, if pages were missing, these were missing since this manuscript was assembled. Building from this claim, Boone argued that the codex does not therefore allow for missing sheets, because there is no evidence of broken pages and, given the pattern of the leather strips, this would have meant six or more extra pages would have been added after the codex had originally been completed (Boone 2006: 107).

I agree with Boone that there is no reason to think that pages of Codex Laud have been cut out or are missing. Here, I offer additional arguments for this claim, which are based on the physical observation of the codex. The clue, I claim, lies on its covers.

On the obverse cover, the one that does not have alphabetic writing on it and which in my view gives beginning to the manuscript, the upper right corner is a bit detached. There we could observe with our bare eyes a greyish substance, which turn out to be white once seen with the help of a magnifying glass. At first we thought this substance was gypsum, which could correspond to the painting coat of one of the so-called missing pages (Figure 1). Particularly on this cover, Lewis (1996: 285) reported traces of white particles suggesting they belonged to a fixative substance.

Figure 1. Upper right corner of cover without alphabetic writing of Codex Laud.

On the reverse side, the other cover which has alphabetic writing on it, the upper left corner is also detached. Here, we could also see the bare surface on the downside part of the cover and the remains of the same grey-white substance (Figure 2). We also saw that the skin surface of that side of the strip – that is, the upside part in contact with the cover – was “naked”; i.e., without any layer of gypsum. The appearance of gypsum could be verified in other parts of the codex where the white coat is there or had eroded. Furthermore, with the aid of a magnifying glass, even the epidermal textures of the skin could be seen. Attached to the skin, there were traces of some grey “plaque” too. Near to the lower left corner of this same cover, we observed a red stain on the edge and on the skin. This gave us a parameter to distinguish if there had been traces of paint on the inner surfaces below the cover, which would supposedly belong to that “hidden” painted page (see arrow on Figure 3). On the lower left corner itself, the cover is also detached and we could see the grey-white substance again, only in this place it was slightly fibrous and filamentous. As a result of this observation, we conclude that the “plaque” is not gypsum, because, as we will report further below, this shows up differently in other parts of the codex as solid and cracked pieces (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Upper left corner of cover with alphabetic writing with bare skin surfaces and traces of white-greyish matter; a) view from top; b) view from beneath (photos by K. Mikulska).

Figure 3. a) Lower left corner of cover with alphabetic writing with traces of filamentous substance; b) Arrow shows spot of red ink (notice the differences of skin when covered with gypsum and when it is not).

When we take into account the manufacturing process of the codex, where the gypsum is put first and then the colours, we find further reason for rejecting the claim that substance under the cover belonged once to one of the missing pages. If this were the case, then we would expect to find pieces and traces of both gypsum and pigments. But colours are definitely absent between these two skins; we see only a white matter. Another reason to think that this white is not gypsum is the fact that sticking the cover with gypsum in between would have turned out into very unstable bond, since, as can be observed when handling the other pages of the codex, the gypsum can come off “easily” in pieces.

Burland (1966: 9) also noted the presence of something white below on this side cover, which he suggested was the same gypsum that can be found on other parts of the codex. Snijders (2016: 35, fig. 1.14) did not observe the white colour in these raised parts of the codex, but, instead, noted the existence of a brown residue. We think the brown colour he reported is simply skin coloration.

There are few studies on the glues used in codices and the Mesoamerican world. Snijders (2016: 34) points out that due to their organic origin, they are difficult to identify unless it is by invasive methods. There are some studies in the conservation area that have identified adhesives derived from orchids and that have been used in paper offerings in the Templo Mayor and feather art (González Tirado 2006). From colonial sources, such as the 1570 work of the physician and botanist Francisco Hernández de Toledo, it is known that glues were mainly obtained from the *Epidendrum pastoris*, *Bletia campanulata* and *Bletia Autumnalis* species (González Tirado 2006). Frances Berdan (2007) investigated the *tzacuhkli* (or *tzauhtli*), which is a generic term used in historical sources to refer to a gum derived from orchids. In her research, she reproduced this substance and other glues in the laboratory, and experimented with them. Her research showed that orchid glue was likely used for fine works such as in feathers, fans, flags, textiles, and ornaments in cotton and paper; resins such as copal and pine were likely used to bind stone mosaics; and beeswax was likely employed for feathers and repairs, as with the mask of King Pakal of Palenque. Orchid glue leaves clear residue, while resin glue – such as copal – leaves thick, dark residue.

Snijders (2016) mentioned other possible uses of these glues in the context of the codices. He argues that glues were not only for the material support, but also probably used for fixing the pigments. Such glues include rabbit glue, coming from the skin of this animal, with less strength but still flexible; bone glue, not so strong and inflexible; fish glue, coming from the bladders, bone, or skin, and capable of adhering to porous surfaces; and Acacia gum, such as the one coming from the mesquite tree commonly used by artists for colouring. However, Snijders (2016) rejects the use of glues of animal origin and resins such as copal, since heat would have been required to make them liquid and this would not be appropriate for the animal skins. In addition, we know that resins dry and solidify very fast (Berdan 2007: 18), which would not allow one adequate time to move or correct the position of bonded and covered strips. Berdan does not mention this explicitly in her study, but I think that beeswax would have been a good option for gluing the strips and covers in codices (perhaps in combination with resins), since it can easily be made liquid, it dries slower, and it is flexible and impermeable (Berdan 2007: 18). However, beeswax is white when it is just produced, but its colour changes to yellow and brown when dried. Thus, we are still uncertain about which adhesive could have left the white residues on the codex.

HOW WAS CODEX LAUD MANUFACTURED AND ITS CONTENT PLANNED?

According to the Florentine Codex, the *tonalpouhque* (i.e. the experts in the calendar and divination) were also responsible for making their own codices (Sahagún 1577: 246v). Hence, the *tonalpouhque* would have had the knowledge of materials and pigments, which, as Dupey (2019: 203) tells us, was a powerful skill since the adept painter-writer was the one capable of "animating things" through his talent and proper colour management. With this in mind, we could conclude that whoever made Codex Laud was also thinking about its content. In this way, Codex Laud can be said to have been created by some who had in mind their ability to be able to use the codex in accordance with his or her experience, needs, and preferences, both practical and aesthetic. Without doubt, the dimensions, length, and therefore number of chapters were premeditated. In other words, creating a codex was a project with deliberate planning; if the format was large, perhaps it was destined to become a reference book, to be read motionless; if it was a small project, then perhaps it was intended to be mobile and transported; if it was too long, it was designed to show many chapters and therefore many different subjects; if it was too short, it was perhaps intended as a summary to present concise and abbreviated matters. Codex Laud presents very selected and specialised chapters, represented in a summarised, concise, and abbreviated way (see Rojas in prep. for more details and comparison between codices). Given this fact and when compared to our narrow universe of codices, we can conclude that Codex Laud was designed as a mobile object that could be easily transported and taken on travels.

For a better comprehension of the images on the codex, the materiality of the book must be observed and taken into account. Which chapters are at the beginning and at the end extremes? Is there any logic for the chapters that are in the so-called obverse and reverse? What is the sequence and order that the chapters follow? Five of the precolonial codices of the Borgia group have a certain number of strips of skin of relatively the same size glued together. In these cases, as in the case for Codex Laud, it is inferred that the codices were planned to remain very regular in their material support. Hence, it is very likely that the number of chapters and pages to make them fit was known beforehand (however, Cospi does present several blank on both sides). In other words, it was not a simple "notebook," which would be filled with data randomly. In fact, even though we can assume that it was always better to have space left over, even the blank spaces were likely designed with some coherence between chapters in mind.

Furthermore, it would have been necessary to think about which pages would constitute the obverse-front and reverse-back sides of the codex. We consider the obverse the side on which no unions of strips are apparently visible, which is commonly taken as the beginning of the manuscript. For Codex Laud, this side is entirely used, since no cover needed to be placed on this side. On the other hand, since the codices we have are so regular

in the extension of the skin strips and the folding back and forth of the strips has the same amount of pages, this obliges to leave two pages on the reverse to be used as covers. This means that there were two less pages to be filled with content on this side. For the codex to “close” well, the length of all strips would either have to be the same or would have to be proportionally adjusted to take into consideration two space-pages of this kind (Figure 4).

Figure 4. a-d) Different angles of Codex Laud folded or closed (note neatness of cuts and folds on each side).

A description on how this *tonalamatl* was made according to our observations follows here.

Getting the skin and treating it (tanning)

The material of this manuscript is animal skin. Due to the gypsum coat on the codex, it is not possible to infer which animal this skin was sourced from, in contrast to the case of the covers, for which we have convincing evidence that the skin was taken from a jaguar (Snijders 2014). On some parts where the gypsum has fallen off – for instance, on the edges of the codex – the skin shows the same appearance as the skin of the covers. With magnifying glasses, it is even possible to see the texture of epidermis and therefore the support material is for sure not paper. The skin of the interior pages, unlike on the covers, is slightly lighter in color; namely, a lighter brown-grey. This is probably due to being less exposed than the

covers and its gypsum coat, which was once all over these strips. The skin on some parts of the reverse cover (where the alphabetic letters are written) is thinner than that on the inside. They are slightly different in colour and thickness, but both are skin.

As a first step to make the codex, it would have been necessary to obtain animal skin. Most researchers agree that skin from codices was deer. However, other skins such as jaguars, pumas, or canids could have been used (Maldonado and Maldonado 2004). As Snijders (2016: 11) suggests, the skins had to have been from a relatively large animal to produce strips that were one meter long approximately. From the Colombino Codex, some hairs were analysed on the skin. Without full certainty, the results indicated the skin belonged to pronghorn (Álvarez 1966). Once the skins were obtained, they went through a tanning process (for details on this subject regarding codices see Álvarez Icaza 2014; Snijders 2016; Maldonado and Maldonado 2004). For this process to be successful, it was necessary to flay the animal's skin a short time after death to avoid decomposition, then to remove muscles with great care, wash the skin, let it dry, put salt on it, remove the hair with lime, then macerate it with some tannin substance, and let it dry again and smoke it to finish the process (see Cervera and López 2000 for identification of this process through colonial sources). In the case of the covers, since the animal hairs on this skin were left intentionally, the skin was not shaved and certainly the tanning and smoke procedure had to have been different.

Cutting, folding, sewing and glueing strips of skin

Once the skins were ready and properly turned to leather pieces, they had to be cut to size. The dimensions of the strips, in the case of Codex Laud, seem to have already been predetermined according to its content and uses: a short, concise, portable book with few chapters related to death, marriages, goddess Tlazolteotl, a ritual procession, ritual procedures with offerings, among other things. On the edges of the codex skin, you can still see dark, straight lines, surely made with some help (a ruler) to follow the cut neatly. In the case of Codex Laud these strips have more or less the same dimension (approx. 1 m. long each, four in total, reaching 3.96 m, Álvarez Icaza 2014: 88). On pages 7 and 21 of the obverse, on the upper edge of the left side, and pages 25, 26, 27 and 28 of the reverse, on the upper edge, the lines that served as a guide for the cut are noticeable; they are grey, surely made with charcoal (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Examples of grey lines on the top edge for cutting the skin, on pages: a) 7; b) 26.

Figure 6. Seam on fold between pages: a) 4 and 5, or; b) 43 and 44.

Figure 7. Second seam between pages: a) 13 and 14, or; b) 34 and 35; c) view when codex is closed; d-e) closer look at the cross-stitch.

Each strip was folded to create the shape of each page. This fold was done before sticking the strip to another strip. For this codex, squares were made symmetrically (15.5 cm height x 16.5 cm long). For each strip, 6 squares or pages were made, which would have required 5 folds each. Some very hard instrument (Burland 1966 suggests a bone awl) or even heat was probably used to generate the folds. In this process, the skin had the risk of wearing away, so much so that it might have even broken. In the codex, there are two seams in these folds. The first between pages 4 and 5 on the obverse or pages 43 and 44 on the reverse,

located on the upper edge (Figure 6). The second seam is between pages 13 and 14 on the obverse or between pages 34 and 35 on the reverse, almost on the lower edge (Figure 7). In the first case, the seam is just at the fold and top edge, and it looks as if the strips have been "knitted" to create "a missing skin" where there was a break or just a very thin surface. In other words, it does not appear to be something amended but rather reinforced. This "new tissue" was covered with gypsum, but now the gypsum is missing and therefore the new tissue can be seen.

On page 5, approximately 2 cm to the left of this seam, there is a hole in the skin, which is also seen on the reverse page 43 (as noted by Lewis 1996). On page 5, on the gypsum around the hole, marks of a very fine textile, like a gauze, can be seen. This shows that there was a patch applied to cover that hole in an area where the skin is very thin. This gauze or textile once had gypsum on it that covered the hole seamlessly (Figure 6a, similar holes also reported on Codex Borgia, Mikulska 2015).

The other stitching, the one on pages 13 and 14 or 34 and 35, looks different. It consists of a cross stitch between the two pages, which reinforces the fold, in an area where the skin is also very thin. In two of the small holes through which the thread passed, the holes are visible. In the other two holes, the thread remains in place and looks fibrous (made up of several fine brown fibers). The stitch holds the skin tight making it rumpled (Figure 7a-b). Here again, the gypsum was placed on top but as the threads bulge this coat, it was easier for these areas to have more wear and tear.

Figure 8. Flap for joining strips on page 12 where the thickness of leather was reduced.

Along with this process, the leather strips were joined, probably folding the first strip to the measurement of the pages and then cutting the excess leaving a flap of approximately 4 cm to join it to the next strip. At the joint of the flap and the new strip, the skin thickness was reduced. This is clearly visible on page 12 and the flap is visible on the back on page 36 (Figure 8). The aim of reducing the skin thickness was to achieve greater uniformity and the same thickness on the surface of the interior of the codex. This same process is also observable in the Borgia and Vaticano B codices (Mikulska 2015). In Codex Laud, all the flaps are visible on one side. Hence, this side is considered the reverse, because even when the flaps are well joined and thinned, they leave a bulge when covered with gypsum which becomes darker due to rubbing over time (Brothertson 1995:180, considers this as the obverse, contrary to all scholars' opinion). The unions are visible on pages 29 (3 to 3.2 cm

wide, slightly curved so it is wider to the center, and notoriously thin), page 36, (3 to 3.2 cm wide), and page 41 (4 to 4.3cm wide, very noticeable, and not so thin) (Figure 9). The flap on page 36 was slightly wider than the codex since in this part the strip is slightly narrower, so one corner of the flap is "outside" of the book strip, but still not detached (Figure 15b). This contrasts with the corners of the covers indicating the glue of the interiors has been preserved better, probably due also to the thick gypsum coat.

Figure 9. Flaps visible for joining strips on the reverse, pages: a) 36, and; b) 41.

Coating with gypsum

Afterwards, the codex was covered with gypsum. MOLAB analysis (Buti et al. 2014; Domenici et al. 2019: 161; Grazia et al. 2019) have shown that the composition of this white layer is a mixture of anhydrite (calcium sulfate CaSO_4) and gypsum (sulfate calcium hydroxide $\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) with variable traces of calcium carbonate (CaCO_3). Gypsum could be used as the generic name for these compounds. Because of this, following Domenici, it is more correct to speak of gypsum and not plaster or stucco, names commonly used and whose chemical composition is different and more often found on other materials. This gypsum coat is called a “preparation base” by Álvarez Icaza (2014). It was applied with brushes and other instruments such as spatulas and surely in several layers, as also suggested by her and Lewis (“smoothing tools or a stiff brush”, 1996: 278). The inner folds were reinforced with some hard, long, and thin instrument, which left a sort of groove as a mark. Burland (1966) and Álvarez Icaza (2014) mention that gypsum was not applied to the outer folds, but this could simply be because the book has been rested on these areas and there the “white” may have been lost due to wear. It is unsurprising, therefore, to find that the gypsum is better preserved in the inner folds, but due to the unfolding and opening of the codex, in these areas the

gypsum is cracked. In the external folds, where the gypsum has fallen off, the skin of a grey colour can be observed, which is the same as in other areas of the codex where the gypsum layer has eroded (also noted by Álvarez Icaza 2014: 96). With the gypsum gone, these areas become like ash greyish, similar to a wall which had a lime coat. This is very noticeable in the first chapter of the codex of the reverse, pages 25 to 32, as it is the most worn out (see further for more details). It is in these areas where you can perceive the original thickness of the gypsum. It is also possible to observe that the pieces of gypsum left over are very fragile and in danger of continuing to come off (Figure 40).

Figure 10. Brush strokes on gypsum on page 16 (fragment from digitised photos in possession of Bodleian Library)

Figure 11. Grooves left by the application of gypsum with hard tool (stone smoother?) on pages: a-b) 7; c) between 11 and 12 (photo in possession of Bodleian Library); d) 35

On page 16, one can see examples of the marks left by the instruments that applied the gypsum (as also noted by Álvarez Icaza 2014: 91). These marks have the appearance of brush strokes (Figure 10). Other marks that look like grooves are also apparent, which were likely formed by applying gypsum with a harder instrument (perhaps a lithic smoother?). These are particularly clear on pages 6 and 7 near the upper fold, on page 11 moving to page 12, and on page 32 and 35 (Figure 11). In some cases, such as on page 27 near the top edge, on page 32 in the center, and page 40, there are elongated, sometimes parallel, marks on the gypsum, resembling striae or features that come from the rugged surface of the skin (Figure 12). On some other parts, like on the fold between pages 33 and 34, the skin underneath seems rugged and uneven (Figure 12c). These features are similar to the texture of inner skin where muscles were attached. However, to ascertain why the skin has these marks, it would be necessary to remove the gypsum layers on the codex.

Figure 12. Examples of possible striae on the skin that have left marks on the gypsum on pages: a) 27; b) 33-34; c) 32; d) 40 (fragments from digitised photos in possession of Bodleian Library, except b, taken by Mikulska)

Sticking the covers

After being covered with gypsum and folded, the covers were glued. Both covers are 1 to 2 mm larger than the pages at the extreme ends of the codex. On these edges, between the codex and the margin of skin left by the cover, there is a layer of gypsum. This layer is not thick, but is, in fact, rather thin (Figure 13 and 16). This thin layer of gypsum most likely corresponds to a last coat of white before applying colours. As already mentioned, we doubt that the end pages of Codex Laud had been painted or correspond to the page(s) that other

researchers assume are missing based on their content. The observable evidence in the codex, with covers attached (with a white substance) where no pigments or gypsum are observed, supports the view that the codex was conceived with 24 pages on the front, 22 pages on the reverse, and two covers that sealed well (Figure 14). Another subject to investigate further is whether or not the glue of the flaps is different from that of the covers, since the flaps are all very well joined in contrast to the covers, which are naturally more subject to friction and manipulation (Figure 15). Another aspect to notice is the fact that the skins on the covers were not tanned (already documented by Álvarez Icaza 2014: 90). As pointed out by Snijders (2014), the skins on the covers were very probably from jaguar, which was considered to be a very special animal. It is likely, therefore, that the fur of the animal was deliberately left on the skin of the covers for both protection and aesthetic reasons.

Figure 13. Covers that are a bit larger than the codex with a thin layer of gypsum on the inner side, seen on pages: a, d, e)1; b-c) 24 (notice the irregular cut on the edges).

Figure 14. Covers glued to the codex but on corners tending to become detached, on pages: a) 46; b) 24.

Figure 15. Flaps' glue better attached, probably due to reinforcement of gypsum coat, pages: a) 41; b) 36; c) 7

Applying last layer of gypsum and polishing it

A last layer of white paint (or very diluted gypsum) was applied to the codex, which served as a surface to apply the colours and as a binder that served to fix all previous coats. This surface is very smooth and in some places it is even shiny, as if it was burnished (also noted by Álvarez Icaza 2014) (Figure 16). This finish could be achieved not only by this binder, but also by sweeping with a brush or a sort of fine sandpaper. Among the possible binders, the orchid *tzauhtli* might have been a good option, because according to the aforementioned studies, it dries white. Other option could have been the sap of prickly pear cactus (*nopal*) which is also used by artists and architects when finishing walls with lime and plaster, because it leaves a shiny surface. According to MOLAB studies, in some areas of the codex, signals of protein were recognised, which may be due to the kind of binder used, though it is also possible that it was the skin on the background that was detected (Buti et al. 2014).

Figure 16. Last coat of gypsum, which clearly shines with light. Feet are also on top of red framing line, page 1

Painting and writing: giving order to space

Only after applying the last layer of gypsum and polishing it were the colours applied to the codex (see Dupey 2015, 2019 for an explanation on the manufacture of organic-inorganic pigments by precipitation with salts or combination with clay). Logically, each side of the codex would have been painted at different times, allowing each side to dry and thus avoiding spoiling the fresh ink. It follows that the gypsum layer, including the last layer of burnished and glossy gypsum, had to be there on both sides before starting to paint, otherwise images could have been ruined if turned on its back to prepare and paint the other side. Regarding the colours, one should expect to find differences in hue between the obverse and reverse sides, precisely for the same reason that it would not make sense to apply pigments to both sides at the same time. Indeed, this was exactly what we found. In the next section, we will argue that even colours for individual chapters were applied at different times and, perhaps, by different hands, since the shades of the colours used in each chapter vary significantly.

Figure 17. Page 39 which shows a small line on the inner fold for guiding horizontal red frame, clearly made before the pictorial scenes. Note also sketch lines between the blue and white-foam of waves

Figure 18. Examples of images on top of red lines on pages: a) 2; b) 3, and; c) 8

Red lines on the codex have the function of splitting pictorial scenes within each page or in-between pages. They were the first step in applying colours. The vertical red lines on the folds are noticeable in the first chapter of the obverse and almost all of the reverse, Chapters 6 to 10 (see below my proposal of chapters). Both vertical and horizontal lines for dividing the pictorial spaces of the book were made by extending and opening the codex, for sure after deliberation about the contents of each chapter.

The red lines were almost certainly made with the help of rulers or straight instruments, because they are perfectly made. On page 39 on the inner fold, there is a small line that would have served as a guide for the drawing of the red line that runs horizontally and divides in two bands, which belong to different chapters (Figure 17). On page 1, one of the red lines reaches the cover, which proves that the covers were already in place before the colours were applied. On pages 2, 3, 7, and 8, it is noticeable that the red frames of the bands were made before the figures and designs, since the latter are clearly superimposed on top of the red lines (Figures 16 and 18). This is clear, for instance, in the image of the jaguar thrones or the feet of the figures on these pages, however, it is worth to highlight that the white of toenails was retouched. On page 39, this also occurs with the figure of the sea situated on the red line that divides the upper and lower bands (Figure 17).

Figure 19. Sketch lines visible on pages: a) 37, and; b-c) 44.

As already mentioned, the impression that the codex gives is that the content of the codex was planned before the manufacturing process began. This is clear when one considers the content and number of chapters of the codex, which have been implemented in such a way as to indicate careful and premeditated thinking about the number of pages required. After making the frames for pictorial scenes with horizontal and vertical red lines, the outline

of motifs and designs would have been made with charcoal pencils. After this task was complete, the contour lines would have been covered with black ink, which we know was carefully carried out, since in few parts of the codex the lines of that sketch are still visible. Álvarez Icaza (2014) calls these sketch lines as the “preparatory drawing,” which could still be seen in some designs that were left without a black ink outline.

I agree with Álvarez Icaza that we can see the charcoal sketch on page 39 on the reverse on the line that divides the blue of the water and the white of the waves (Figure 17). However, I think that the same charcoal sketch can also be seen in the tail of the fish in this same area and in the heart found in the lower band. On page 37, there is also a sketch line in the breast of the lady in yellow with a snake on her neck, though it could also have been produced while making the black outlines, as the unwanted outcome of a little smear of ink (Figure 19a). Other faint sketches are seen on page 44 at the feet of the old woman in the upper band, as well as in the river of the lower band (Figure 19b,c).

Painting and writing: making the outlines of designs with black ink

After the space of the codex had been appropriately ordered, the black outline of the figures was made. Importantly, this was done before applying colours, as already proposed by Lewis (1996) and thoroughly demonstrated by Álvarez Icaza (2014: 112-214). This contradicts the claim made earlier by Burland (1966), who thought that the colours were applied first and then the black outlines defined. Álvarez Icaza brings forward the possible type of instrument that was used for this task, which left an incision on the borders of this outline. As she noted, the precision of the contour lines is surprising, very sharp, firm, without hesitation, and of the same thickness throughout the lines. Thus, the tool used was likely a reed or something similar to what we know today as a fountain pen, with a firm tip that left that fine incision in the gypsum while at the same time allowing the constant flow of ink (Álvarez Icaza 2014: 118). She also noted that such a colour application techniques would be very similar to those used in the production of the Codex Fejérváry-Mayer.

Something important to notice in Codex Laud is that the painter-scribe, in the one aberration from his or her otherwise impeccable skill, occasionally used too much ink when producing the black contours (or, perhaps, he or she did not make sure to leave the ink to dry before closing the codex) which caused some transfer of black ink to the opposite pages. For example, on page 13 near the inner edge next to the image of the pulque pot, you can see a little of the figure of the skull found on page 14 (Figure 20a). Similarly, on page 23 at the bottom of the page near the Lizard sign and the foot of the god Tlaloc, there are some small regular black circles that correspond to the spacers on page 24 and also, even more clearly, the hand and knife that the god of death holds on page 24 (Figure 20d). On page 41 in the upper left corner, there are some transfers which belong to page 42: the skirt of Tlazolteotl which has many stripes (Figure 20e). And in the lower band in the right quadrant below the bowl with offerings, there are some marks of the bowl rope also with offerings from page 42 (Figure 20b). On page 45, in the lower band on the right-hand side, in addition to the ink being smeared on the scene, traces of black and yellow paint that correspond to the wood (*ocote*) splinters on page 46 can be seen (Figure 20c). None of these transfers, for the last one with yellow paint, have traces of colours which is also an argument in favor of the black lines

being made before applying the colours. The latter could also just be a palimpsest that became visible after a big washed out of that page.

Figure 20. Examples of black ink transfers on opposite pages: a) 13-14; b) 41-42; c) 45; d) 23-24; e) 41-42 (fragments from digitised photos in possession of Bodleian Library, except b) and c) by Mikulska)

Painting and writing: colouring ... but following an order

Once the black outline of the figures was applied, the spaces were filled in with colours. For this, we also have good reason to think that they were filled in following a certain order. As we will discuss further in the next section, the reason we should take this view is due to the fact that there were parts of the codex that were not completed and left colourless seemingly without intention. In the codex, red is always there, and so too is blue and green (although in some chapters blue and green do have a hue that is very similar to each other). Grey was also applied in this first group. Then came the yellows, creams and oranges. Colours were applied in at least two layers (and possibly more), and some contour lines may have been highlighted to always appear very sharp and solid.

Examples where it is seen that red and blue were applied after the contour line are found in Chapter 1, pages 1 (red on the teeth of the sign Grass, blue on the eyebrow of the sign Serpent), 4 (red at the ends of arrowheads and bones), 5 (red on jaw teeth, armband ornaments, and clothing), 6 (red on toes and pyramid stairs), 7 (red on nose of character with face paint and blue on its ornaments, red on the jaw teeth of the sign Death, Figure 21a,b), and 8 (red on the tip of the arrow and lines on the brazer -Figure 21c) and blue on the sign Water); in Chapter 2, on page 9 (red on the edge of the seat with jaguar skin and blue on the wings of the bird), on page 12 (red on the blood), and on page 13 (blue on Tlaloc's clothing); in Chapter 3, page 21 (red on the temple stairs and red line on offerings ?, blue on the bracelet of walker with flowers); in Chapter 4, page 24 (all details in red, Figure 21f); in

Chapter 6, pages 34 and 38 (hands of men in red, Figure 21d) and 37 (the red on the heart and flower, Figure 21g); in Chapter 7, page 39 (red on the fish's eye and face of Quetzalcoatl, Figure 21h), page 41 (red on armbands of Tlazolteotl, Figure 21i); in Chapters 8 and 9, pages 41 and 43 (red on the stairs of the temple, Figure 21j); and Chapter 10, page 45 (on the heads of the bone-awls, Figure 21k).

Figure 21. Examples of red paint on top of black line of contour, pages: a-b, e) 7 (notice on e) re-application of black lines); c) 8; d) 34; f) 24; g) 37; h) 39; i) 41; j) 44; k) 45

Other examples of the application of grey on top of the contour lines are in Chapter 2, on page 13 (on the scrolls of the clouds) and in Chapter 7, page 39 (on the face and clothing of the goddess). Cases for green on top of the outlines are in Chapter 3, page 21 (the green on the rubber ball) and Chapter 9, page 39 (the green of the offerings of grass).

In Chapter 4 on pages 24 and 25, the process of applying colour is better observed and comprehended since it was evidently left undone. Here red, blue, and green were applied in layers. It is particularly noticeable that the red is clearly diluted compared to the rest of the codex, meaning it had only one coat, clearly applied on top of the black outlines (Figure 21f). The blue colour is very close to green, with both colours perhaps best defined as a shade of turquoise. We can infer, therefore, that both colours were likely applied at the same time. Although both the blue and green are more solid than red (especially the green), the lack of a clear distinction between the two suggests that if another layer had been applied, then perhaps

a better differentiation could have been made. Grey was also applied with this first group of colours. It is also relatively solid, but appears here a bit lighter than in other parts of the codex. This also applies to the cream colour, which had only been applied in a single layer and only placed in some details: in the sign Deer on page 23 and the bodies of Mictlantecuhtli and the god with spear-thrower or *atlatl* (Xiuhtecuhtli?) on page 24 (Figure 22). It is, therefore, clearly missing on other designs that could have been filled-in with this colour, for instance, the pot on page 23 and the skin of Xipe Totec on page 24. In summary, there are at least two groups of colour application. Blue, green, red and grey were first colours applied, followed by yellow and creams.

Figure 22. Cream colour on body parts almost not perceptible and red very diluted, page 24

Álvarez Icaza (2014) thinks that the yellow colour is very unstable in the codex, because it easily degrades. However, in our observations this colour rather reflects different moments of its application, either with just one layer or with two coats (Figure 23-24). This is especially noticeable when comparing the obverse and reverse side. The former shows a more uniform and solid yellow, probably due to more than one layer of application. On the reverse, yellow is very faint and diluted, sometimes observable as if it was a watercolour, and some other times observable only in close combination with orange. Was the *tlacuilo* experimenting between these two colours? For example, in Chapter 5, on page 25, one of the feet of god Mictlantecuhtli is clearly more yellow than the other, the latter being more diluted and watery (Figure 23a). On the same page, the body of the *tlacatecolotl* has a slight yellow part and the rest is cream, which has clearly been superimposed on yellow (Figure 23b). In this chapter, on the first two pages (25 and 26), there are parts of the human figures where the cream is combined with strokes of yellow and there is no clear intention in fixing the cream (Figure 23c). Therefore, it seems yellow was applied first, and then cream, but in this section some parts ended up just with the yellow. This is particularly apparent when only one of the feet or ears of human figures are coloured in cream. It is possible that in these first two pages it was left pending to reaffirm either with more yellow or a coat of cream pigment to make it darker.

Another example lies in Chapter 7, where Tlazolteotl is protagonist, on page 40, where the legs of the goddess above the knee are yellow, although one is more diluted than the other. On the darker one, even a kind of “drop” – or accumulation of paint – is visible. Below her knees, the cream (or more orange) hue was applied, evidently on top of the yellow (Figure 24a). Lewis (1996: 283) has already noticed something strange on page 42, where orange has been applied to one of the spacers at the top, as if it were a combination of red and yellow and not just a solid colour. Her observation supports my hypothesis that the *tlacuilo* experimented with the colours yellow, cream, orange, and red, first applying yellow in small areas without letting it dry and then applying a very watery red, making the combination of orange right there, as if exploiting a watercolour technique of painting.

Figure 23. Yellow and cream not solid or firmly set on pages: a-b) 25; c) 26 (photos b-c are fragments from digitised photos in possession of Bodleian Library)

Figure 24. Examples of diluted yellow on the reverse, pages: a) 40 (fragment from digitised photos in possession of Bodleian Library); b) 41; c) 44; d) 45; e) 42; f) 36

More examples of highly diluted or single-layered yellow are found in Chapter 6 on pages 36, 37, and 38 in the spacers of days and bodies of women (Figure 19a); in Chapter 7 on page 42, where brush strokes of a very diluted yellow can clearly be seen on the body of the goddess (Figure 24e); in Chapter 8, on page 39 at the feet of man in the temple and page 41, on the body of the man with white clothes (Figure 24b); in Chapter 9, on pages 43 and 44, on the roofs of houses or temples (Figure 24c); and in Chapter 10 on pages 45 and 46, on the bodies of both women (Figure 24d). Elsewhere, the *tlacuilo* seems to have taken care to ensure that yellow does not exceed the black contour lines; for instance, when avoiding to go over those small, millimetric, and equidistant lines from the hairs of jaguar fur in Chapter 1 on pages 1 and 2 (Figure 18a) and in Chapter 2 on page 9.

The last chapter on the reverse side – i.e. Chapter 10 on pages 45 and 46 – may also be unfinished. The colours red, blue, green, grey, and yellow have been applied here, although the latter is very diluted. However, some figures of animals, clothes, and objects appear white, whereas in other parts of the codex they appear with colour. For example, the turkey here only appears with red on the head and legs, but the turkey on page 32 also has grey on its body and beak (Figure 25a,b). Although it does not appear elsewhere, the coyote (I do not think it is a dog because it does not have ears like the sign Dog in the codex) is left white. But it is rare to see coyotes depicted as white, because coyotes (*Canis latrans*) – and even the hairless dogs – are ordinarily depicted as being grey or brown in colour. The skirts of both women also appear very white. The skirt of the woman on page 45 has a horizontal stripe outlined, but is left without colour, which seems unusual. Similarly, the pot on page 46 appears white, but in other parts of the codex where there is a similar scene – for instance, when pouring water on offerings – the pots are depicted as cream with a circle in the middle (Figure 25c,d). Likewise, the offerings that are being burned in this ritual performance are left white, when on the previous page and also below this scene, the ocote bundles represented there – which are identical in shape – appear yellow and tied together with a red dotted ribbon. The smoke that emerges from the depicted ritual scene is white, whereas on other pages where offerings are burning – such as page 41 – the smoke represented has grey and cream colours (Figure 25e,f). Another example of scrolls that could be smoke is in Chapter 2 on page 12, where the god is surrounded by a shape with grey and yellow scrolls. Lastly, the hair of both women on both pages, although with black lines, lacks of the grey background. For these reasons, this last chapter may also have been in the process of being completed; and perhaps this process was paused due to the large smear of black ink on page 45, which was left uncorrected. This seems to have happened when applying the grey and yellow, hence the cream is completely missing which belongs to the last group of colour application.

Given the order of colour application and the presence of some colours on similar figures, we may also be able to infer that other scenes remained incomplete. The first is a scene in Chapter 8 on page 39, where it is possible that the rectangular figure under the bundles of grasses and offerings with the heart, the feet coming out of this figure, and the path, were left white. In this scene, the yellow colour of the heart, the wood splinters of *ocote*, and the flames of fire is very faint, so it is possible that no second coat was applied. Another scene is on page 43 in Chapter 9 in the lower right quadrant where the crossroads and the reptile-earth were left suspiciously white. Furthermore, the woman's skirt on page 37 in Chapter 6 could be seen as a last unpainted detail, because all of the other the skirts in this

section have colour. One last instance is clearly seen in Chapter 3, on its very last part, on page 22, where offerings, spacers and signs were left unpainted. For this, a mistake of ink smear seems to be the reason for such missing which, as well with page 45 of Chapter 10, will be further explained in the next section.

In overall, I think that blue, green, and red were the first set of colours to be applied. Grey could well have been applied as an intermediate colour. Later, yellow, creams and oranges were created by mixing them together in combination with white. Afterwards, finishing touches were added, for example, repainting black outlines and using a sharp pointed instrument to place coloured dots on some details.

Figure 25. Evidence in favor of the claim that Chapter 10 remains incomplete, note turkeys on pages: a) 32; b) 45; pots, smokes and hairs on pages: c) 46; d) 1; e-f) 41 (all fragments from digitised photos in possession of Bodleian Library)

On some cases outlines seem clearly redrawn so as to make them clear and sharp. Examples of this can be found in Chapter 1 on page 1 on the red paint on the penis of the beheaded man and the green of the bundle of grasses (Figure 13d), on page 3 on the eyebrow and eye of the deer, on page 5 on the red tongue and beak of the sign Eagle, and on page 7 on details of the sun, hearts, and blood (Figure 21e). The same can be found in the Chapter 2 on page 9 (the tree) and page 10 (the teeth and tongue of Tlazolteotl); in Chapter 3 on pages 20 and 21 (in details of blue and green); and in Chapter 5 on page 26 (tongue of sign Eagle) and page 27 (the grey and black bird on the foreground of a grey plant).

The use of different instruments to apply pigments and fine points and lines is also noticeable. For instance, the bars for the numbers of Chapter 10, which seem to have been made with a stamp. On page 45, the stamp had rounded corners and on page 46 it had angular corners. The precision of tiny lines, made with symmetry and pinpoint accuracy is awe-striking, like on the edges of skirts and tunics, or in the sandals worn and thorns and awls held by Tlazolteotl on page 39. Small black lines or very small dots seem to have been done with a stick or something firm with sharp points. As Álvarez Icaza has suggested, something similar to a fountain pen may have been used. This is particularly evident in the mandibles

and skulls of the Death deities, or next to them, and on the signs of Grass where tiny yellow and red dots were placed (Figure 26a,c,d,e). These can be seen, in Chapter 3 on pages 18 and 20; in Chapter 5 on pages 25, 27, and 31; in Chapter 8 on pages 39 (this one without yellow dots) and 42; and in Chapter 9 on page 44. It is also worth remembering the tiny hollow circles on the skin of Jaguar signs (Figure 16 and 18a) and the indication of fur with equidistant small lines on animals, day-signs, and arrows (Figure 26b). The small details in colour cream in Chapter 1, on feathers and knee caps, and bracers is also surprisingly perfect (Figure 26 f).

Figure 26. Examples of small details of dots, lines, and colours on pages: a) 20; b) 17; c) 31; e) 25; f) 8

Correcting mistakes

In the process of colour application, specially on black outlines, some errors were made. However, these were rather few in this manuscript. Logically, if mistakes happened, it was necessary to wait for the ink to dry and then to apply more gypsum, which would cover and “erase” the flaws. For example, on page 8 in the lower band on the right side, the thumb of the warrior's hand is clearly disproportionate when compared to the other fingers or his other hand. Also, the yellow colour is not uniform and therefore this might be the result of a correction (Figure 27a). In another example on page 37 in the lower right quadrant, the man of this couple holds a drum, which is set at a very straight angle to his arm, suggesting that the white was overlaid to correct a possible error (Figure 27b).

At the bottom of page 31, near the outer edge, there are hints of ink lying underneath the gypsum making a circle similar to the day spacers (see above on that page). Here it seems we face a palimpsest; or the image of something that was covered with gypsum for a new creation (Figure 27c). Another possible example appears on the lower corner of page 44 where there is a red thin line looking rather transparent through the upper gypsum, but perhaps this was just a marking line for the creation of the red framing lines (Figure 27d).

Figure 27. Probable correction of mistakes and palimpsest on pages: a) 8; b)37; c) 31 (fragment from digitised photos in possession of Bodleian Library); d) 44

Other mistakes appear due to ink smears on the gypsum, which were (obviously) not corrected. There are two cases that stand out, because they lie on scenes that were not finished and, perhaps, these mistakes disrupted the process of having pigment applied. The first, on page 22, an evident smudge of black ink can be found on the second bundle of offerings from bottom to top. This group of offerings along with other figures of calendrical designs that are situated at the left side of the page, next to bar numbers, were left uncoloured. As Lewis (1996: 291) suggests, it appears that water spilled on this area (Figure 28a). It seems that this mistake was the cause for not colouring this left section of this page, which awaited to be corrected. Nonetheless, the rest of the chapter presents all range of colours in the palette. The second smear is at the bottom of page 45, in the area below of uncoloured figures of offerings and bar numbers. Here, there is a great sweep of black ink coming from the bar numbers that even reaches the upper band, staining the feet of the woman depicted. It does not seem that there has been any effort to delete the scene and, in fact, it is possible that water was spilled onto the page and was then smeared along the page (from left to right). It should be mentioned that inks were not erased with water, but, rather, with gypsum. As I mentioned before, there are indications that this page was yet to be filled with colours, which perhaps was a task to be done after proper application of more gypsum and remaking of designs. However, it could also be possible that the page remained without all colours set and years or even centuries later, already in Europe, somebody spilled water

and damaged the codex. As said by Mikulska (personal communication) this might well have been the case, since the codex seems so well executed that leaving such a large stain would probably not be the style of the *tlacuilo* of Codex Laud (Figure 28e).

In general, there are no big mistakes and instead there are merely drops or minimal ink residues on the codex. For example, on page 3 on the deer's face there is some black ink (noticed by Lewis 1996) and on page 10 the heart near the outer edge has very faint traces of red ink, as if a little of the pigment has been smudged (Figures 28b,g). On page 14 on the grass of the offerings, we find some sort of dirty stains of black ink (noticed too by Lewis 1996, Figure 28d)). On page 19 on the knee of god Quetzalcoatl, it seems that the black ink of the outline has been smeared (Figure 28c). On page 20, the owl has a black or grey ink stain on one of the wings (also noticed by Lewis 1996), and near there, further to the left near the edge, are spots of a similar colour (Figure 28o). On the middle of page 24 on the outer edge, there is a drop of blue, right on the teeth of the earth (possibly an ink of more recent times, Figure 28n). On page 27 on the bottom edge, slightly to the left side, there is a dot of intense black ink, which looks like an intentional drop that had not been corrected (Figure 28k). On page 28, there is a small red ink spot on the yellow body of the central character (noted by Lewis 1996, Figure 28i). On page 30, there is a black spot almost in the center, similar to a brush stroke (Figure 28j). On page 32, the nude man inside the temple or house has traces of black ink smeared on his hand, which could also be an example of an outline that has been redrawn without being left to properly dry (Figure 28l). On page 38 in the upper left quadrant near to the scorpion, there is a smear of dark red paint (Figure 28h). On page 40, there are also traces of blue ink on the bottom edge (Figure 28p). On pages 42 and 43 right on the fold of the codex, there are dots (drops?), one red at the bottom and another yellow at the top, respectively. On page 44 on the upper left quadrant, the offerings have bits of smeared ink making the whole scene a little smudgy and “dirty” (Figure 28f) Finally, on page 45, the woman’s clothing features a black dot, perhaps from the sharp instrument that was used for the outlines (Figure 28m).

Figure 28. Mistakes, smudges, and smears of ink on pages: a) 22; b) 3; c) 19; d) 14; e, m) 45; f) 44; g) 10; h) 38; i) 28; j) 30; k) 27; l) 32; n) 24; o) 20; p) 40 (a-d, g-i, l, o, are fragments from digitised photos in possession of Bodleian Library)

WERE COLOURS APPLIED TO CODEx LAUD CHAPTER BY CHAPTER?

Álvarez Icaza (2014: 138) suggested that each of the sections or chapters of the codex were carefully planned and painted separately, implying that the colours were not placed at a single moment nor were the same colours used throughout the codex. Therefore, we can infer that leftovers of paint were not used to fill adjacent sections. Likewise, the work of Domenici and the MOLAB team (Domenici et al. 2019; Domenici et al. 2017; Grazia et al. 2019; Buti et al. 2014) showed that the codex has a reasonable variability in colour shades, especially in green. The chemical composition of this colour also showed variability, which is reflected in hue differences in different parts of the book. This indicated that there were deliberate decisions to apply colours according to different spaces. However, these studies did not create a complete and precise map of the variations in pigment hue and chemical composition throughout the codex, which could have added sound support for this hypothesis.

Álvarez Icaza's (2014) idea that the manuscript was painted by sections, implies that the selection of colours was not random and that the colours themselves had an important symbolic content. Therefore, when looking at the codex we paid a lot of attention to the distribution and choice of colour palette, taking care to assess whether or not the choice of colour provided support for the claim that colours were applied at different moments of time. Indeed, this is what we found. In this sense, it is possible that different *tlacuiloque* had been responsible for different chapters. However, in terms of style there is no outstanding evidence to verify this conjecture. To a certain extent, as Álvarez Icaza (2014) suggests, pages 23 and 24 might stand out for their possible “different hand,” especially due to the detailed elaboration of scrolls in the sky of page 23. Still, it is commonplace and intuitive to conceive of pages 23 and 24 as a single chapter.

The colour palette of the codex is composed of 5 “primary” colours: white, black, red, blue, and yellow. The “secondary” colours are green, pink, beige, orange, brown, and grey, which derive from the former when diluting them with gypsum or mixing them with each other. This coincides with the chemical analysis done through spectroscopy by MOLAB (Buti et al. 2014; Domenici et al. 2019; Domenici et al. 2017; Grazia et al. 2019). These studies used technology that emits light of different ranges – such as infrared, ultraviolet, or X-ray fluorescence. Then, by measuring the absorption of this light, it is possible to identify the chemical elements in inorganic pigments and some of the components of organic dyes. Likewise, macroscopic studies in codices and bibliographic sources are helpful to find clues on the materials that were used to paint this manuscript (e.g., Elodie Dupey 2015, Dupey and Álvarez Icaza 2019, and Dupey 2019, as well as those of Álvarez Icaza (2014) made directly on Codex Laud itself). These works indicate the possible natural resources used to create the colours and offer the names of the colours in Nahuatl as well. They also provide other data of

social context to add on our knowledge on the production of codices (see Rojas in prep. for details on each of Codex Laud's colours and their natural origin based on these studies).

For our colour analysis on Codex Laud, we used the RAL K7 Classic fan (213 Colours, 2019 edition). We dedicated time to trying to recognise differences in the shade of colour between chapters. For this, it was important to set criteria for the identification of chapters at the outset. As has been done compellingly throughout codices studies, these were based mainly on two aspects: 1) the change in distribution and composition of the images, and 2) the different groups of days depicted showing different calendar permutations. In the codex, these changes are relatively clear, except for some cases described below. Moreover, following Álvarez de Icaza's hypothesis, a third criterion based on variations on colour shade, has now been added to distinguish distinctions between chapters. By working with these three criteria, the chapters set-out in Table 1 were identified.

Table 1 takes into account composition, calendrical count, and consistency in tonality. All hues identified are presented, but the dominant colour tonality is shown in bold letters (except for one case where this could not be well established). It is worth noting that we only compared the changes of shades within each side. It is highly unlikely that the manuscript was flipped right after painting one section to continue with another on the opposite side. This would have ruined the process of drying and colours would have been transferred or smeared. Still, this well planned codex – which was painted thoughtfully per chapter – was left unfinished on both sides.

In general, a high consistency was achieved in the production of the shades of pink, orange, yellow, grey, and red and blue. However, in the green colour there is a great variation in hues, with some even touching upon blue and brown. Evidently, this is why MOLAB identified two types of green (Buti et al. 2014). Our colour analysis gives support to the hypothesis that the colours vary according to chapters. After considering composition, calendrical counts and colours below, the arguments for the identification of chapters is explained.

	OBVERSE				REVERSE			
Chapters	1. Two 20 Day-Cycles (from day Grass) pp. 1-8	2. Gods of the Divided Trecenas (in 8 and 5 days) pp. 9-16	3. The Procession pp. 17-22	4. Tlaloc, Patron of the Calendar and the First 2 Trecenas (of cycles of 65 days) pp. 23-24	5. Aspects of Death pp. 25-32	6. Prognostications for Marriage pp. 33-38	7. Four Aspects of Tlazolteotl. 8. Two Times 20 Signs and their Offerings 9. Five Sets of Days (from the Trecenas of the North) pp. 39-44	10. Counted Offerings pp. 45-46
RED			3002 Carmine Red			3002 Carmine Red	3002 Carmine Red	3002 Carmine Red
	3003 Ruby Red	3003 Ruby Red p. 9	3003 Ruby Red p. 17					
	3027 Raspberry Red p. 6 y 7	3027 Raspberry Red		3018 Strawberry Red				
					3033 Pearl Pink	3033 Pearl Pink		
BLUE			5018 Turquoise Blue	5018 Turquoise Blue		5018 Turquoise Blue	5018 Turquoise Blue	5018 Turquoise Blue
	5021 Water Blue p. 4	5021 Water Blue			5021 Water Blue	5021 Water Blue		
	6033 Mint Turquoise					6033 Mint Turquoise		
	6034 Pastel Turquoise p. 1			5009 Azure Blue p. 24				
GREEN			6000 Patina Green				6000 Patina Green	6000 Patina Green
			6028 Pine Green				6028 Pine Green p. 44	
	1027 Curry			6033 Mint Turquoise	6033 Mint Turquoise			
		7008 Khaki grey p. 9						
		8000 Green Brown			6004 Blue Green p. 28		6025 Fern Green	
						6011 Reseda Green		
Grey	7037 Dusty Grey		7037 Dusty Grey	7037 Dusty Grey		7037 Dusty Grey		
		7036 Platinum Grey				7030 Stone Grey	7030 Stone Grey	
					7039 Gris Cuarzo			
YELLOW	1018 Zinc Yellow	1018 Zinc Yellow				1018 Zinc Yellow	1018 Zinc Yellow	1018 Zinc Yellow
			1016 Sulfur Yellow		1016 Sulfur Yellow	1016 Sulfur Yellow	1016 Yellow Sulfur	
CREAM	1001 Beige		1001 Beige		1001 Beige p. 31 y 32	1001 Beige		
	1015 Light Ivory p. 8			1015 Light Ivory	1015 Light Ivory	1015 Light Ivory		
		1013 Oyster White						
ORANGE	1034 Pastel Yellow						1034 Pastel Yellow	
PINK		3015 Light Pink				3014 Antique Red		
Notes	Zinc Yellow corresponds to a shade with two coats of paint. Blue is a turquoise shade. Grey without good adherence. Blue is a turquoise shade	Red better corresponds in between hues here mentioned. Green has a brownish tonality	Green changes, more fixed, more turquoise. Clear variation between green and blue.	Green and blue are almost identical. Red has only one layer, therefore is lighter. In p. 24, blue is slightly lighter than Azure Blue. Chapter is not finished; yellow (cream and orange) is missing.	Strokes are clearly seen in yellow color, diluted and watery. Green and blue are very similar. Cream is very light, only on last pages it, has 2 coats. Green shows adherence, does not crack.	Differences in green than previous chapter. Blue is difficult to identify; lies in between these 3 shades, a faint blue, watery. Yellow is sometimes diluted but rather consistent, solid.	Strokes are seen in yellow; corresponds to Sulfur Yellow when it is light, one coat. Green cracks.	Chapter is not finished; grey is missing.

Table 1. Colour variation between chapters of Codex Laud (colours taken from <http://ralcolorchart.com/ral-classic>).

Obverse

1. Two 20-day cycles (from day Grass). Pages 1 to 8

The first eight pages of the codex have relatively the same composition: two broad bands running horizontally, with respective lower bands running beneath. In the broader bands, there are scenes that have human figures, gods, animals, or offerings. In the narrow bands, there are the calendar signs. On the first four pages, there are red framing lines dividing the bands in a vertical sense, creating at each page four quadrants. Vertical red lines in the narrow bands create, four or five spaces per page (Figure 29). The calendar signs follow a consistent sequence: beginning on page 1 at the lower band with the sign Grass and running to the left on the following pages, then moving to the upper band on page 8 to continue to the right, and, finally, ending with the sign Death on page 1. From page 5 to 8, there are no vertical red lines dividing bands and, therefore, each sign corresponds to an image of the broadband (except on page 7 in which the bottom image covers the entire record, corresponding to two signs on the calendar). Due to the slight change in composition of these vertical lines, I thought initially that they could belong to different chapters. However, the colour hues are consistent between both sections, so there is no justification for dividing them. Nevertheless, it is striking that from page 6 onwards there is more detail and an impeccable use of the colours of orange and grey in knee pads, bracers, feathers, and feather balls. However, other reasons could be found on the lack of vertical lines in the second part of this chapter upon further analyses of the content of these pages.

Figure 29. Diagram of Chapter 1, Codex Laud

Anders and Jansen (1994) think that this is not the section that begins the codex and rather it should be considered an intermediate section connecting the reverse and obverse. This view is unique among scholars of the codex. For them, therefore, the reverse is the initial side of this manuscript. However, I place this section as the first section due to the fact that the sequence of the calendar signs and their respective images are similar to mantic scenes similar to the unquestionable first chapter of codices Borgia, Vaticano B, and Cospi, whose calendar sequences are, by contrast, shown *in extenso*; i.e., as a complete 260 days. In Codex Laud, this is the closest we have to that kind of distribution and representation.

In this chapter, the colours are relatively consistent, except for red and blue. The latter is more variable. In the following chapters, the colours do differ; especially in regards to green, which turned out to be an important parameter to identify “the change of hands,” or, at least, of the changing of colour batches. Here green is clearly differentiated from blue. For the other colours – for instance, red –, although the same hue is repeated in the next chapter, it appears here slightly lighter. Blue comes in one of three shades. However, in the following chapters blue gets a less variation, with only one consistent shade. Yellow stands out for its

solidity, unlike in many other chapters. This implies that here, at least, it was applied in two coats.

2. Gods of the divided trecenas (in 8 and 5 days). Pages 9 to 16

In these eight pages, the main images where the gods are located occupy almost the entire space of each page (Figure 30). At the bottom, running from right to left, the calendrical signs are depicted. With the help of circle-spacers at the top, there is the indication of abbreviating days in the 260 day calendar count, which specifically shows groups of thirteen days or trecena. In this case, the counts should be made by pairs of pages in which the first signs correspond to the first group of 8 days (shown on pages 9, 11, 13, and 15) and in the second signs correspond to the last 5 days of each trecena (on pages 10, 12, 14, and 16). In total, the whole count of 260 days is depicted.

Regarding colours, it is clear that red, blue, grey, cream, and green change in comparison to the previous section and the following ones. The case of green is worth noting, as it is a good indicator of change, becoming a somewhat more brown tone in Chapter 2. Although similar, this shade will not be repeated in the rest of the codex.

Figure 30. Diagram of Chapter 2 of Codex Laud

3. The procession. Pages 17 to 22

In these six pages, there is no indication of calendrical signs, with the exception of page 20 and 22. On the first, there is an owl and next to it the sign Water with three circles – i.e. 3 Water – and one other circle at the other side of the bird making reference to 1 Water or perhaps just indicating the “beginning.” A specific calendrical date – such as 3 Water – is rather rare in this type of mantic and prescriptive book. Therefore, I believe that it is the indication to follow ritual at the sign Water, which had to be continued for three more days. The same applies for the signs and circles on page 22, which lie next to bundles of offerings and bar numbers. The signs are, from bottom to top, Reed with 9 spacers, Reed with 8 spacers, Flower with 5 spacers, and Reed with 2 spacers. Spacers stand for days of rituals to be performed starting on the day indicated with the number -bar numbers- of bundles or counted offerings shown. The composition of the pages does not contain vertical red framing lines (Figure 31). Each page has four figures in each quadrant, except for the last one, which only has two on the right side. This section, as discussed above, remained unpainted. The figures are all anthropomorphic, except for the owl on page 20. Most of them have open legs, so it gives the impression of movement, as if they were walking. Some also hold canes or carry burdens (*mecapal*). Overall, then, it seems that these figures are travellers (see similar chapter in Fejérváry-Mayer : 35-43). Other figures are depicted in ritual scenes, such as the drilling of fire (p. 17), human sacrifice (p. 17), or taking offerings to a cave (p. 22).

The colours here are clearly different than in the previous chapter. Red, blue, yellow, and cream change their tone slightly. In the case of blue, its hue is consistent throughout the chapter. Green, our indicator of change, is not only radically different from the previous sections, but its tone is closer to that of the blue hue. There are slight variations in shade with few appearances of different reds and greens.

Figure 31. Diagram of Chapter 3 of Codex Laud

4. Tlaloc, patron of the calendar and the first two trecenas (of cycles of 65 days). Pages 23-24

These two pages are usually considered to be two separate chapters (Anders and Jansen 1994; Álvarez Icaza 2014; Burland 1966: 24; Boone 2007: 247). Although they depict logical calendrical compositions by themselves – i.e. they can be understood separately – the same colour hues are used in both, which indicates that they were conceived – or at least, created – together. If this was indeed the case, the calendrical signs also match and function in agreement. On page 23, Tlaloc appears surrounded by the 20 signs of the calendar, framed between the sky and the water (a body of water, possible the sea or a lake). On the next page, which is also the last page on the obverse side, the scene somewhat obliges one to turn the codex 90° and then also 180° (this it reminiscent of the central pages of Codex Borgia). On this page, there are only four calendrical signs: Crocodile, Death, Monkey, and Vulture, whose presence points to the particular division of the 260-day cycle into groups of 65 days. In each sign, there are 25 spacers, giving a total of 26 days from the aforementioned signs (or, alternatively, 2 trecenas). Each of these four sets of days are distributed at the corners of the page, along with a god who faces a couple of other gods at the middle. Thus, gods and signs are painted on a terrestrial surface, and in the center there are three images: an eagle, a sun with a god in the center, and the image of a human sacrifice. Thus, the scene at the center is depicted as taking place in the sky. The relevant issue to mention here is that this sequence of the calendar is initiated by Tlaloc, painted in style and with details very similar to the previous page; for example, holding the same snake in his hand. This similarity in style and the fact that Tlaloc is the presenter of the calendar in both pages further supports the argument that these two pages belong together (Figure 32).

Figure 32. Diagram of Chapter 4 of Codex Laud

As for colours, on these two pages there is a new important revelation. Grey and blue are the same or, at least, are very similar to the previous chapter. However, green and red change. The proximity between green and blue is remarkable, so much so that it is easy for them to be confused during bare eye observation. To differentiate them it is necessary to pay closer attention. The case of red is significant as it seems is the only section of the codex that was a faint, with a “washed out” hue. We think this is due to there having been only a single coat of paint applied in this instance. In general, it is worth noticing that these two pages have a rather “white” appearance. In fact, there are colours that were not applied at all; most notably, yellow. This becomes clear when looking at the headdress that Tlaloc wears on page 23. This headdress has the unquestionable shape of a jaguar, which, as in other parts of the codex, is coloured yellow with details and “fur” in black lines. However, this is not the case here and it is also not the case with the sign Jaguar next to Tlaloc’s mouth.

Other elements that obviously should go yellow are: the corn plant, the flower sign, the lips of the snake and lizards, the beak of the eagle, and the hair of Tlaloc. Most notably, the yellow colour on the skin and body of the slaughtered person is missing on page 24, which has led researchers to interpret this figure as an “albino” (Anders and Jansen 1994). Other details in yellow that were missing on page 24 are the outline bands of the sun, the beak and feathers of the eagle, the hair of the solar deity in the center and as patron of the Death trecena, the flayed skin and ear in the headdress of the god Xipe Totec, and further details in the clothing of Quetzalcoatl and the Tezcatlipoca gods. As for the cream colour, it can be said that it is present, although in a very faint hue perhaps created with only a single layer. On page 23, cream can be identified in the sign Deer and on page 24 it can be seen on the bodies of Mictlantecuhli and the god with atlatl (Xiuhtecuhtli?). Since this colour is perceived as more variable in other parts of the codex – either in combination with yellow or somewhat in the process of experimentation –, it is possible that it was still to be applied in various instances; for example, on the skin of Tlaloc and on the pot being poured on the left bottom corner of page 23.

As said above, these two pages could well constitute separate chapters due to their differences in composition (the arrangement of the images in the pages’ space is clearly different) and to the presence of calendrical signs that themselves make up logical calendrical sequences (20 signs on page 23 and 104 days or four times 26 days starting from a 65-day division). However, we should also not rule out the possibility that they belong to the same mantic “narrative.” Nonetheless, the presence of Tlaloc as patron of the signs on page 23 and then as “presenter” of the calendar of four groups of 65 days on page 24 is relevant. The division of the calendar into groups of 65 is known in the calendars registered in Zapotec communities as *cocijos*, which in turn are associated with the god Cocijo, the god of Lightning. Cocijo is analogous to Tlaloc: both are gods of rainwater, rainmakers, and cloud controllers. In this way, Tlaloc shows himself as the main deity of time and also of earth space (see Rojas in prep.). Hence the identical shades of colours blue, green, red, and grey in these two pages and the fact that the yellow colour is missing in both, offers a little more support to the claim that both pages belong to a single chapter.

As a last comment, it is worth saying that the lack of yellow in these pages was noticed by Agostino Aglio in the Kingsborough edition (1831). In fact, he made a pictorial proposal to fill in void spaces with colour that “should have” been coloured in yellow and cream (the latter of which turned out to be more orange in his edition). His experienced eye when copying numerous codices made him, in my opinion, very successful in filling-in the

places where we would expect to find yellow (Figure 33). This fact becomes remarkable since no scholar after him had noticed the missing colours.

Figure 33. Pages 23 and 24 of Codex Laud in the Kingsborough (1831) edition, volume in Bodleian Library (notice how this copy fills in the voids where yellow had to be present)

Reverse

5. Aspects of death. Pages 25 to 32

This chapter coheres neatly with the previous chapter, which presented the groups of 65 days on the obverse. It is a composition similar to that of Chapter 2, where the day signs are aligned at the bottom of the page and a broader scene occupies most of the space above. These scenes mostly depict the gods of death – namely, Mictlantecuhtli, Mictatecihuatl, and Tlazolteotl – performing in mantic or ritually-prescriptive way (Figure 34). As for the calendar, there are sets that refer to the groups of 65 days or *cocijos*, with indications of certain relevant days in correspondence with the mantic or ritual images. This is also made clear with the help of spacers at the top. As in Chapter 2, the sets of days should be counted in pairs of pages, two by two, presenting 4 and 6 days in the first pair, 6 and 4 in the second, 6 and 6 in the third, and 5 and 8 in the fourth. The day count, however, is not complete and only 180 days are depicted.

Figure 34. Diagram of Chapter 5 of Codex Laud

As already mentioned, it is only worth making comparisons concerning colour when we view the companion chapters for each side of the codex. Colours in this chapter are very

consistent. Red and grey are not only stable but also unique shades found in the codex. Blue, although a bit variable within the chapter, is rather similar to green. The only somewhat unstable colour is yellow, but this is because it has been noticeable applied with an abundance of water, as brush strokes can easily be seen. As we will see, the yellow on this side is a variable and rather unstable pigment in terms of its application.

6. Prognostications for marriage. Pages 33-38

This chapter is easily recognisable due to its composition and content. It has no calendrical signs; simply circles that in other chapters would serve as spacers, but here they serve only as counters (Figure 35). They refer to the sum of the numbers according to the calendrical name of the couple close to being married or that are a prospect for marriage. Since the number possibility in names ranges from 1 to 13, here the options from 2 to 26 are depicted. Similar chapters are to be found in Borgia and Vaticano B codices. The chapter is composed in the following way: each sheet is divided into four quadrants with red framing lines, except for the last two sheets, 37 and 38, whose upper register had to include one more space so that all the counters could fit. In each painting, there is a couple – a man and a woman – who interact with offerings, self-sacrificial instruments, ornaments, and clothing, animals, trees, or children (there is only one painting where there is no couple and there only one woman appears with two children, p. 36). All this refers to the forecasts that the couple could have for their lives.

Figure 35. Diagram of Chapter 6 of Codex Laud

The colours in chapter 6 can be said to have changed when compared to previous chapter. The colours of red, blue, grey, and yellow are all different. Green is no longer a shade of “turquoise” and turns into a more “vegetable” hue. Blue is somewhat difficult to identify and lies somewhere in between the three shades that were identified. And yellow, even when the shade was found, has only been applied as a very diluted and watery substance. Here, a shade of pink also appears, which clearly is the same red use, but now having been mixed with gypsum (page 36).

7. Four aspects of Tlazolteotl. Pages 39-42

8. Two times 20 signs and their offerings. Pages 39-44

9. Five sets of days (starting from the trecenas of the north). Pages 43-44

I gather three chapters in this sub-section, which each share the space of multiple pages and have a relatively similar composition. What’s more, there is no variation in colours between them (Figure 36). However, it must be stressed that these do constitute different chapters due

to their clearly different calendrical sequences and their symbolic content. However, they also complement each other well (the last two chapters begin with a highly similar scene). Hence, in the same way as with last chapter of the obverse (i.e. pages 23 and 24), despite the differences in composition and calendrical sequences, the same colours indicate a single moment of writing and painting by the *tlacuilo*. Unlike the last pages of the obverse, however, here the calendrical sequences cannot be easily combined, and therefore they must be considered as separate chapters. Lending further support to this hypothesis of differentiated chapters is the fact that the last chapter has a more compact format, which gives the impression that it was perhaps “inserted” in the space left over.

Figure 36. Diagram of Chapters 7 (grey), 8 (white), and 9 (slash) of Codex Laud

The arrangement of these chapters consists of dividing the pages into two horizontal bands with a red framing line. This horizontal line was likely made by extending the codex, but clearly not extending it from the previous chapter, because the red lines do not match with those on pages 38 and 39. This supports the claim that paint was applied to these three chapters in the same moment of time.

The chapters incorporate vertical dividing lines, which serve the purpose of creating different arrangements of the space. The first chapter is located in the upper register of pages 39 to 42, with vertical lines of division in the inner folds. It shows all 260-days cycle divided in four groups of five trecenas each (or 65 days in each page). The second chapter is located in the lower band, reaching one page more than the previous chapter; namely, page 43. In this lower band, there is another narrow lower band, running parallel and with its respective red framing line that houses the calendrical signs running from right to left. On each sheet, there are between 6 to 8 signs (6, 7, 7, 6, 8, and 6, respectively), which correspond to two times the cycle of 20 day-signs (40 days). The mantic or prescriptive scenes are located in the wider registers (or lower quadrants), two per page, except for the first scene, which spans the entire length of the first page. The third chapter is presented only on the remaining two pages: pages 43 and 44. It seems as though the previous chapter left this upper register “open” and available for a third thematic inclusion. Good use was made of this space by introducing compact squares with the aid of red framing lines; 2 on the first page and three on the second. It shows a strange sequence of five groups of days which start on the signs of the trecenas of the north, as indicated on the first square, however, only the first sequence of signs are indicated further. The division of days is 10, 10, 13, 12 and 7, respectively in each square. The depiction of signs and spacers abbreviates a total sequence of 260 days.

Colours are constant throughout these three chapters. They even have less diversity than within other chapters in the codex. Red, blue, grey, orange, and yellow are all consistent. Yellow has the same quality as in other parts: very diluted and watery. It is also worth nothing

that orange, has been applied over a coat of yellow in some instances. Green again is our parameter to measure the different moments of colour application. In this case, it turns back to be a turquoise hue with just one place showing a more vegetable tone.

10. Counted offerings. Pages 45 and 46.

This chapter may also have belonged to the previous sections. The colours are the same as and its content is closely related to Chapters 8 and 9. However, I will distinguish the chapters in this analysis, due to a drastic change in composition and the clear shift in the content to focus on counted offerings (a similar shift occurs in Chapter 3). Another reason to separate this chapter from Chapters 8 and 9 is because of its unfinished painting state. This unfinished state resembles Chapter 4 and, particularly Chapter 3, which also presents an incompleteness that might have been the reason behind those uncorrected mistakes. Nonetheless, a major flaw such as in this case, seems not to qualify for the skills of our painter-scribe.

The images are arranged into two horizontal bands divided by a red framing line that runs along the two pages. Furthermore, there is another vertical segregation of the images at the inner fold between them (Figure 37). In the upper band of the pages, there are scenes that explicitly depict the performance of rites with the indication to perform them at particular times. On page 45, it is suggested that one ought to begin the rites on either the signs of the Dog or Flower, though it could also be 1 Dog or 1 Flower as calendrical dates. I am inclined, however, to the former option, and therefore conceive of the circle next to the signs as symbol for “beginning.” On page 46, the beginning is on the day Water and it is suggested that one ought to continue the rites for 8 more days due to the spacers next to it. On the lower bands, there is the indication of numbers for the offerings to be made., Bundles of wood splinters are also depicted on both the upper and lower bands. On page 45, another beginning at sign Water is suggested and, on page 46, the flower may well represent the sign Flower. The number of offerings to count is shown in the form of bars, which is a distinct feature of this type of chapter, although this feature is also visible in codices Fejérváry- and Cospi.

Figure 37. Diagram of Chapter 10 of Codex Laud

Regarding colours, red, blue, green, and yellow are the same as in previous chapter. The only pigment missing is grey and possibly also orange. Figures that may have been intended to have been coloured grey are: the body of the canine, the hair of both women, the feathers of the turkey, and details in the smoke that comes out of the offerings. We can make this inference because the same figure have a grey colour in other parts of the manuscript. The orange colour was possibly also on the clothing of the woman of page 45, the pot, and the smoke on page 46 (Figure 25). On page 46, it seems that the bundle of offerings in the upper band should have been yellow, but was left unpainted. Other colours also seem to be

missing, such as in the elements in the lower band, which indicate the offerings to be made. On page 45, the offerings – among them an egg and a conch-shell – were left white, but have been ruined by a big smear of ink. Probably, the *tlacuilo* had the unfulfilled intention to correct this untidiness, as mentioned before.

Lastly, it should be mentioned that Anders and Jansen (1994) argue that this chapter gives an introduction to the first chapter on the obverse side. For them, therefore, this chapter functions as a logical continuation of the codex, which would occur when one flipped the codex over. Their reasons have mainly to do with the content, in particular day 1 Water and the 8 Water days depicted on page 46, which are taken to have been indicated on the first chapter of the obverse that gives a start to calendrical counts of days on the lower and upper bands respectively. They connect 1 Water of the reverse with the indication of 5 Reed on the first quadrant of page 1 on the obverse. In my opinión, however, this thesis does not hold, because this is not 5 Reed as a calendrical date. I agree with Boone (2006) that this figure refer to spacers of days not depicted, whereas the Reed belongs to simply to reeds of arrows. Therefore, I do not think that Chapter 1 nor Chapter 10 make a count of concrete calendrical dates, which is to be discussed in detail elsewhere (Rojas in prep.). It should also be mentioned that there are clear colour differences between Chapters 10 and 1, in part due to their appearance on different sides of the manuscript. Moreover, their content does not seem to be coherent: Chapter 10 giving indication of offerings and rituals one ought to make, whereas Chapter 1 refers to auguries of the count of the 20 day signs. It does not appear, then, that they were made explicitly to be used or read contiguously.

SOME DATA ON THE BIOGRAPHY OF THE CODEX

In this section, I will consider a few details that speak about the life that the codex has had in its nearly 500 years of existence. Some of this data may mark the physical integrity of the book since it was still in Mesoamerica, perhaps even in its actual use as an aid to experts who made use of the information pertaining to the calendar and its prognostications and prescriptions. Other data tell us about the codex's path into Europe until it reached the Bodleian Library. In either case, the information is hazy. It is still unknown where exactly the codex was produced in Mesoamerica and we do not know where the codex left the New World before arriving to Europe. Moreover, we do not know from whom and how William Laud acquired the codex. Some ideas have been offered in this regard, mainly by Anders and Jansen (1994) and Burland (1966). However, these two authors were mistaken in their conclusions about the year of acquisition. By correcting their claims, we offer new data that may shed further light on the question of who owned the codex before Laud.

Stains and globs

Throughout the codex, there are pages featuring sticky, wax-like elements, sometimes as minimal as dots, sometimes slightly larger. It seems likely that some of these elements were “splashed” onto the codex, sticking onto the gypsum coat of the document. But in other cases it seems likely that the glob was removed and that in this process oily marks were left on the codex's surface. One possible explanation of these elements is that they are the outcome of manipulating candles near the manuscript.

For instance, on the obverse on page 2 there are small dots in the upper right quadrant. On pages 5 and 6 near the outside edges, there is a waxy element that seems to have been transferred between pages when the book is closed (Figure 38a). Also, in the center of page 5 there is an oily-looking stain (in the shape of a gourd) that also seeped into page 6, as if there had previously been a piece of wax that has now been removed. On page 5, there is one more small dot, that still looks much like wax, in the lower left quadrant. On page 9, near the outer edge, there are some yellowish, waxy spots. Other examples of stains that have passed between pages are between pages 13 and 14 at the bottom near the inner edge, next to the sewing stitch (Figure 7a), and between 17 and 18 in the center (noted by Lewis 1996, Figure 38b). On page 19 in the lower right quadrant, there are spots on the leg of the human figure (Figure 38g).

On the reverse side, there are more of these sticky spots, which could indicate that the codex was more frequently opened on this side. On page 28 near the woman's foot, there is a small sticky-looking stain. On page 29 near the outer edge at the bottom, there is one more stain of this kind. On page 31 on the image of the mortuary bundle, there is a brown waxy stain with tiny hairs visible through a magnifying glass (also noted by Lewis 1996, Figure

38c); perhaps as if some textile or paper had been glued together (probably there was once transparent thin papers between the pages as a means of protection). On page 32 on the upper left side near the turkey, there is a sticky stain, also with hairs attached (Figure 38e). Another example that left its marks on both sides of the pages is on pages 33 and 34, in the lower internal quadrants of the codex. Another sticky, liquid-looking spot is on page 35, in the lower right quadrant above of the woman's face (Figure 38n). And yet another can be seen in the lower left quadrant behind the man's head, whose grey appearance makes the gypsum look filthy. Other sticky pieces are on page 37 in the upper left quadrant over the back of the man's loincloth (Figure 38f) and in the lower left quadrant over the woman's leg. Another spot that is greyish-brownish in colour can be seen in the upper central quadrant above the man (Figure 38h). On page 38 in the upper center quadrant below the spacers, there is another waxy element, and another stain, more similar to something grimey, in the lower left quadrant on the woman's body. Another oily-looking stain is apparent on the bottom band of page 39, on the outer edge (Figure 38i). And another copper colours glob can be seen on page 40 in the lower left quadrant, above the sign Grass (Figure 38l). One more stain with a waxy appearance is visible on page 43 in the lower left quadrant, next to the sign Reed (Figure 38d). Some last globs can be identified on page 45 in the upper band just on the road, and another yellowish glob can be seen on the edge of the woman's *quechquemitl* (type of garment with triangle shape for covering the torsos for women, Figure 38j,o) and there is yet another on page 46 at the center of the upper band next to the pot (Figure 38k).

Figure 38. Examples of sticky stains and globs on pages: a) 6; b) 17; c) 31; d) 43; e) 32; f, h) 37; g) 19; i) 39; j,o) 45; k) 46; l) 40; m) 35; n) 35 (b, g, h, m, n are fragments from digitised photos in possession by Bodleian Library).

Small holes and sunken parts

In the codex, there are some examples of holes. Some of these holes are very tiny and fine, as if they were made with a needle. These were likely made after the codex was painted and covered with gypsum. They were not restored with the traces of gauze (such as is the case on page 5 (Figure 6a) and therefore they seem to have been done in post-Cortesian times. In our observations, we notice needle holes which were symmetrical on pages 7 and 8 (Figure 39e). Another very small hole – which seems had even perforated the whole page, exposing the the cover on the other side – is on page 24 near the outer edge, between the feet of the god Itztli (Figure 39a) (Lewis notices several more other water holes on pages 39, 42, 6, 7, and 8).

There are other parts where something hard seems to have been pushed onto the surface of the codex and has, as a result, left marks on the gypsum. For example, on page 8 in the upper right quadrant just above the spears, there is such a hollow (Figure 39b). On page 41, near the center of the page next to Tlazolteotl's feet, there are orange stains, but these also accompany a concave mark on the gypsum (Figure 39c).

Figure 39. Examples of holes and concavities on pages: a) 24; b) 8; c) 41; e) 7-8

Conditions of gypsum and folds

The conditions of the gypsum on the codex reveals even more about how much the codex was used and manipulated. It is already well-known that the reverse is “dirtier” and more damaged than the obverse (Lewis 1996 is of the same opinion). This state is even more visible on the far right of the reverse (see Chapter 5, Aspects of Death). While this manipulation may have occurred after pre-Cortesian times, it may also be due to more handling of this section in pre-Cortesian times, since that side cover was written with alphabetical writing, giving the impression of the “beginning” of the codex. In any case, this demonstrates that not only is the gypsum more greyish in tonality (as already noted by Burland 1966), but also that it is more brittle. This is evident because the gypsum is even cracked in this section, especially on the edges or places where you would often put your fingers.

By paying attention to these parts – for example on pages 25, 26, 27, 28 and 29 –, it is possible to appreciate and comprehend how the gypsum behaves on the skin (Figures 2, 3, and 40a-e). The gypsum still on the surface looks greyish and filthy. There are parts where the gypsum looks whiter, but this is likely because some recent polish or instrument has been used on the codex and this has made the gypsum lighter. This can be seen on page 15 in the upper right corner, where the number “10” made with pencil was erased and therefore the gypsum has become whiter in this area. If the gypsum becomes fragile, cracks, and starts to fall off, it is possible to see how thick the applied layer of gypsum was. Sometimes, tiny pieces of gypsum even seem to crumble and detach from the skin. On pages 20 and 22 at the outer and upper edges, the gypsum is visibly cracked. However, here the gypsum still looks thick and is attached onto the skin with the layer of paint at the surface that is almost imperceptible. This is also seen on the outer edge of page 38. In the areas where the gypsum has fallen and exposed skin is leftover, the latter appears grey in colour, similar to the texture of a wall that had once had a coat of lime (Figure 2 and 3). This can be seen on page 17 in the lower right corner, just at the edge, where the leather looks similar to chamois and where the paint that the coat lies on is very thin (Figure 40f).

Figure 40. Gypsum reduced on its surface, where it looks white, but also cracked and grey, exposing the leather beneath, on pages: a) 27; b) 26; c) 28); d) 29; e) 25; f)17

It is also noteworthy that in the parts where the application of gypsum was made with a hard and stiff instrument, grooves have been left on the surface. These became dirty over time, with marked grey rims (this is clear on pages 6, 7, 11, 12, 32, and 35; Figure 11a,b). Likewise, on the reverse side on the edges of the flaps, the area has become grey because of being more “exposed” to friction. This is particularly clear on pages 29, 36 and 41. In some parts – such as folds –,the texture of the skin surface also became marked, perhaps due to wear and tear. For example, on page 7 in the lower right area in image of the sun and on page 37 in the upper right corner (Figure 41a). Lastly, on places where there were striae of the skin, the gypsum is more susceptible to soiling, as on pages 4 and on page 40 (Figure 12 and 41b,c). This occurs where there seems that not enough (or not good enough) fixative was added to the last coat of gypsum.

Figure 41. Examples of folds and gypsum worn out on pages: a) 7; b) 4; c) 41

Fingerprints

There are some parts in the codex where the fingerprints – most likely of the *tlacuilo* – have been impressed into the page with black ink. This also shows that the black ink of the outlines was applied with a bit too much ink, causing some problems when it was not given enough time to dry. Examples of fingerprints are on page 12 below and near the offerings, page 16 on top of the sign Grass (these two were also observed by Lewis 1996), page 32 faintly near the Rabbit sign, and page 42 above and near the spacers (Figure 42). Burland (1966) mentions a fingerprint on page 38 in the lower left quadrant, where the gypsum appears greyish in the middle of the couple. For us, that mark went unnoticed, however notorious in the facsimile and photos.

Figure 42. Fingerprints on pages: a) 12; b) 16; c) 32; d) 42 (b and c, fragments from digitised photos in possession of Bodleian Library)

Pencil lines and *ex libris* stamps

In the upper and outer corners of the obverse side of the codex, Arabic numbers for the pages were written with pencil or graphite (Figures 6, 13, and 40). The direction follows left to right in a Western manner. It is not known exactly when these numbers were added, but it was probably between 1635 and 1639 when the manuscript was donated to the Bodleian Library. Most likely this was also the time the *ex libris* of the Bodleian Library was stamped, as on

pages 1, 4, 8, 12, 15, 17, and 21 (Figure 43). Notoriously, these two annotations were only made on the obverse side. According to Wikipedia, this type of *ex libris* belongs to the 1830s. Thus, just for speculation, the pencil strokes observed in some pages could also had happened at this very moment in the 1800s. It could also have been that Agostino Aglio himself accidentally scratched the codex while making the copies of the images with transparent paper. There are pencil marks on page 18 below, in the center (Figure 44d), page 21 on the earplug of Tlaloc and his snake baton (Figure 44c), page 22 in the headdress of the lower figure (these last three were noted by Lewis as well, Figure 44a), page 38 in the upper left quadrant on the man's feet (Figure 44b), page 41 on the man's hand in the lower left quadrant (Figure 24b), and page 42 in the lower right quadrant on the offerings (Figure 44e).

Figure 43. Ex libris of Bodleian Library: a) on page 15 (fragment of digitised photo in possession of the Bodleian Library), b) ex libris circa 1830 (Wikimedia Commons, <http://www.admin.ox.ac.uk/po/graphics/google/bodley1.jpg>)

Figure 44. Pencil strokes on pages: a) 22; b) 38; c) 21; d) 18; e) 42; (a,b,c,d, fragments of digitised photos in possession of Bodleian Library)

Conditions of the covers

The physical condition of the covers also tells us about “what has happened on top of it” or “who has had hands on it.” I would like to start with the description of the cover, which according to my studies should be considered the “beginning” of the codex. This is the cover that does not have alphabetic writing on it. On it there are traces of ink – such as dots and spots – and some lines, like brush strokes without any intention. The ink is black, similar to that found on the other cover. The cover has marks left on the bottom and in the middle by

the path made by insects (this also noticed by Burland 1966). The circular forms sunken on the skin – which have a lighter colour – it seems were also made by parasites. There are also white striae, cracks, and ragged surfaces which corroborate the claim that some of the marks in the inner pages of the codex may well be texture of the skin itself. On this side, no animal fur is seen, and on the back, the skin looks shiny, as if it were the product of having been touched many times. On some parts of the cover, there are marks as if something hard had been leaned upon this side of the book (Figure 45).

Figure 45. Cover of the obverse: a) whole cover; b) details on striae; c) details on bugs' destruction

The other cover – that is, the one with alphabetical script – has more details to comment on. The letters were made with two different ink shades. In the top left, “B. 65 ” has been written in a dark black ink, which refers to section B (of 7 sections) and position 65, where this manuscript was located in 1641 inside the library. With a mixture of inks and different instruments (pens), on the right side it reads “Ms. Laud Misc. 678.” It means: Laud manuscript, miscellaneous 678, which is the classification that the codex had within the collection of the Archbishop. Below, at the center of the cover, it says “Liber Guil: Laude Archiepi Cant: et Cancellarij universit Oxōn. 1634.” This phrase in Latin and abbreviated means: book by William Laud, Archbishop of Canterbury and Chancellor of the University of Oxford, 1634. It is clear that at the time these letters were written the cover already had insect damage, because right on the word *Liber* there is a sunken, white area, apparently caused by insects. As Snijders (2016: 33) mentioned, at the time of writing of these words, the skin no longer had the hairs of what it seems had been a jaguar head skin. As in the case of the obverse cover, this cover has the same whitish circles like bursted bubbles, as well as some traces of the paths of bugs. On the upper right corner, there is a piece of glued beige paper, with a top edge of teeth and a letter “S” still visible. Apparently, this label belongs to the first Bodleian library classification (Robert Minte, personal communication), which kept the first

collections in the old historic building. Around the 1940s, special collections were moved to their present location in the Weston Library building (formerly the New Bodleian Library). There are also striae in the skin texture of this cover. Finally, following the work of Snijders (2014), it is even possible to see the rosettes of the jaguar skin with the naked eye, which look like islands of darker parts on the surface (Figure 46).

Figure 46. Cover of the reverse: a) whole cover; b-c) details of estriae, two different colour inks used, destruction by bugs, and the beige label

Leather case

Little is mentioned about the box or slip-case that protects the codex. But this could be the means of shedding light on the provenance of the manuscript, at least about how it made its way into Europe. Without doubt, the slip-case is a European product. According to Anders and Jansen (1994: 23), it is an Italian-style gilt leather case from the mid-16th century. It is a box made with two square panels and three more that cover the sides, presumably made of wood and covered in leather. Each panel is of a bordeaux colour, with golden inlays using the technique of gilding and goffering. The decoration has squares on the edges and a central rhombus, with arches in the corners and flowers (or, perhaps, stars) in the spaces between. The decoration also includes an undulating motif, similar to a lace filigree in the center. The case shows some wear at the edges and corners, as well as some holes caused by insects (Figure 47).

The gilding technique is a type of decorative binding that applies gold in thin layers to a surface. In many cases, the gold is fixed and glued with heat to covers or backs of books (Carpallo Bautista 2005). It has its origin in the Arabic world in the 13th century. In Spain, where there was a high degree of Arabic and Mudejar influence, gilding started to be used and from here it probably spread to Italy through Naples in the 15th century. The golden

boom happened in the Renaissance, developing strongly in workshops in northern Italy (Carpallo Bautista 2005). From the 16th century onwards, it gained increasing popularity in France, thanks, in part, to the impulse that the printing press had on consumer preferences (Carpallo Bautista 2005: 15).

Figure 47. Leather slip-case: a) with codex inside (note loose-fit of codex); b) one of its sides with bugs and wear damage; c) back side with labels on it.

Goffering consists of stamping dry and hot irons or plates onto surfaces in order to leave a pattern. If used with gold, care must be taken not to melt the gold with excessive heat. This technique has roots in the Middle Ages and was also used among the Arabs. In the 15th and 16th centuries, it was widely used, only later being replaced by gilding in the culture and practices of French binding (Carpallo Bautista 2005). Given the evidence of these techniques and based on the styles described in the literature, we can conclude that the case of Codex Laud has a style of the 16th or 17th century. It is a Renaissance type with simple decoration, with sort of iron in the center, which is more characteristic of the 17th century (see Persuy-Sün Evrard 1999: 19; Redondo Díaz 2014: Plate XII). On the Quarto catalogues of 19th century of the Bodleian Library, there is a handwritten note on this codex saying it is a mid-16 century slip-case. Unfortunately, the case does not have the signature or seal of the bookbinder, something that was often used at the time to allow for the workshop and artists who made the case to be identified. We can only conjecture, therefore, that the box was made in Spain, which would fit with the narrative that the codex first arrived there after being taken out of Mesoamerica.

Inside, the slip-case has a paper lining, also red or Bordeaux in colour. On one of the larger square sides, it has a stripe of slightly different colour next to the open side. This colour is notably darker than the rest of the lined panels. The borders of this paper stripe

lining are detached from the rest of the case. This indicates the box was modified at a certain moment for an unknown reason. The box itself is a bit bigger than the book; possibly to ensure that the fur of the covers were once able to fit in the space. Martin Kauffman mentioned to us that the case does not have the look of the type of bindings that Laud used to put on his books. And Hunt (1973: ix) also mentions that when the archbishop would send his acquisitions to be bound, he would ensure that his coat of arms was put onto the relevant covers or cases, which would also include the name of the binder or workshop as per tradition. These details are missing from the slip-case of Codex Laud, and so it seems that the case was left unchanged after Laud acquired it, probably showing that this item was not of great interest to him.

On the spine of this case, there are five labels, indicating different moments of classification; one at the top and four grouped below. The latter have the following legends: “Laud 65.,” “153,” “Laud 678,” “Ms Laud Misc 678.” We have explained the origin of each of these above, except that of “153,” which is one of the registration numbers for the manuscript in the Special Collections section. The top label is more damaged, but still reads: Liber Hieroglyphicorum Aegyptorum Ms, or “Book of Egyptian Hieroglyphics Manuscript.” This legend, with a letter other than the writing on one of the covers, seems to belong to the times prior to the acquisition of the book by William Laud or perhaps is the letter of the chaplain, William Dell, who was responsible for classifying many of the Laud books (Hunt 1973: x). This is a piece of information that could be verified by conducting further research in the archives of the library, as there one will find lists of the manuscripts written in his own hand.

On a small article for the Mexicolore website, Ian Mursell (2016) thinks that the label of “Egyptian Hieroglyphics” was placed after its arrival to the Bodleian Library; according to Dr. Bruce Barker-Benfield, Senior Librarian who assisted Mursell at that time, this year was 1634 (this short article shows a contradiction because it first mentioned 1636 as the year of donation). He adds that whoever handled the codex made a “wild guess” of its origin and assumes too that Dell could have been responsible for this. Below, I will argue that this label, as well its box, had been inscribed even before Laud acquired this treasure.

1634

In this last section, I dedicate some lines to explore new possibilities for the keeper of the codex prior to it being acquired by William Laud. I make this claim based on the observation that the year 1634 is written on the codex’s cover (Figure 48). This date has often been confused as 1636 (and reproduced by scholars Burland 1966, Anders and Jansen 1994, Alvarez Icaza 2014). In my opinion, the reason for this confusion is because of the widely circulated catalogue of the years 1858 and 1885 (reprinted in 1973), which records the date as 1636 (Hunt 1973) . As far as I can tell, this is a mistake. And to correct it, one should rely on the numbers written in the original catalogue in the 17th century, when Laud had the codex in his possession. When we proceed in this way, another possibility emerges.

When Laud was appointed archbishop in 1633, he formed the habit of writing on his books the year that he had acquired them (note that those he had already acquired by 1633 received that year. See Hunt 1973: ix). In the Bodleian Library papers – the Household Accounts –, there are some references to how he acquired his manuscripts, but these span the

years 1636 to 1641, and unfortunately the references do not always coincide with the actual manuscripts (Hunt 1973). In some cases, he entered whether a document was a gift or the name of previous owners in the book itself, but this is not the case for Codex Laud. Thus, it is not clear in his correspondence how he obtained the codex or in which parcel it came. We know only that whoever previously owned the codex added the label “the Egyptian Hieroglyphics Book,” because this inscription can be seen on the Renaissance-style slip-case.

Figure 48. Year 1634 on the reverse cover. Note that the second cypher, a “6,” is visibly different to the fourth one, which cannot be another “6” as often read in the literature

According to the 19th century catalogue (Hunt 1973), Laud made few acquisitions in 1634. Instead, he set about managing a donation to the library of books that belonged to Sir Kenelm Digby, a courtier and diplomat who had inherited many books from the famous Oxford mathematician and astrologer, Thomas Allen. The transaction of these books was recorded in a letter dated December 19th of that year, where we also found out that they were delivered in a parcel with 235 volumes. It is unlikely that Codex Laud came in this package, since Laud says that he did not open the parcel and respected the books delivered in that way, because Digby had packed them, bound them, and placed his coat of arms on them (Hunt 1973: xix).

We might, of course, have more data on the provenance of the manuscript if we could review the original catalogue that accompanied Laud's books when he donated them to the library. According to the 19th century catalogue, the codex came in the second donation made by Laud, on June 16, 1636. Recall that in this catalogue the year of acquisition by Laud is 1636. Assuming that this year is correct, this implies that the archbishop only kept it for a few months in his private library. Thus, the year 1634 seems a more feasible option for the time of Laud's acquisition. In any case, there is an interesting note in the aforementioned catalogue: right next to the name of Misc. 678 – or Codex Laud – in the list there is a note that says that this book is not with certainty identifiable in the list of donations that Laud made. In other words, without having had the opportunity to check this catalogue from the year 1636 – or from the other donations in 1635, 1639, 1640, or 1641 – it seems that since the 19th century, the donation to which this manuscript belongs cannot be clearly identified. This leaves many questions in the air and introduces a set of obstacles in our search for the origin of the

manuscript in the Bodleian Library (see the cataloging history of the Bodleian Library for further clues in Hunt 1953).

But there may be a search path in the classification of “Egyptian hieroglyphics book” in the inscription on the codex’s slip-case. This title could be a clue to the association of the manuscript codex with someone interested in Hermetic issues; that is, issues concerning esoteric texts, which have been attributed to Hermes Trismegistus. During the 17th century, Hermetica had a close, secret, and loyal group of followers among scholars, philosophers, and mathematicians. To name a few famous participants, Issac Newton, Thomas Allen, and Kenelm Digby were alchemists and therefore followers of Hermetica. Allen and Digby were close to the circle of William Laud at the time he acquired the codex. However, William Laud was certainly not tolerant of such issues, since he was faithful only to Christian and Anglican causes. This might also explain why he was not very fond of Codex Laud, which was not marked with his coat of arms and so was not given a clear classification in his original catalogue list of his donations to the Bodleian Library.

Although we lack firm evidence, it is possible that someone interested in alchemy and Hermetica possessed Codex Laud prior to Laud, thinking that it was part of ancient Egyptian philosophy. As said before, Sir Kenelm Digby might had been a possibility. This option deserves attention, because not only did he have contact with Laud, but also with Spain. When he was young, William Laud – then dean of Gloucester – was his tutor. After a one-year stay in Spain in 1618 (where he accompanied his brother in a diplomatic procession), he came to Oxford under the tutelage of Thomas Allen (born 1540). In 1623, Digby went to Spain as part of the campaign to negotiate the marriage of Charles I with the daughter of King Philip III. On his return, he was given the title of Knight and Charles I granted him permission to be a corsair; that is, to carry out maritime warfare or sabotage enemies in the Mediterranean. In other words, Digby was a pirate approved by the king (Miles 1949). It was in this context that he captured several Spanish and Flemish ships in 1627. In 1628, he fought in Syria, thus gaining fame in England. And then in 1632, Thomas Allen – who had remained close and influential to him – died and Digby inherited his library. In 1634, as a result of the Digby’s depression of having lost his wife, he donated Allen’s books to the Bodleian Library. However, we know for sure that Codex Laud was not among Allen’s books that were given to the Bodleian Library by Digby. And after that time, Digby confined himself to Gresham College, Oxford, where he carried out alchemical experiments and afterwards headed to Europe where he switched his faith to Catholicism (Miles 1949). Keeping himself far from the political problems Charles I faced, he was later accused of murder. He died in 1662.

As a note, Thomas Allen was also a famous astrologer and alchemist, who belonged to a selected circle of knowledgeable and esoteric figures. Among them was John Dee (1527-1608/9), a controversial figure and astrologer in the court of Queen Elizabeth (see biography in Yates 2004). Both Allen and Dee were collectors of hidden books and antiquities. Allen was also acquainted with nobility. In fact, he was appointed as the astrologer of Robert Dudley (1532-1588), Earl of Leicester, a powerful statesman and a favourite of Queen Elizabeth. As with Allen, Dee moved freely (and coherently) between mathematical research and Hermetic alchemy. His library had around four thousand books, specialised in philosophy, mathematics, geography, and esotericism, becoming a renown centre of the intellectual life of Renaissance minds (Szöny 2004). Later in his life, he became renown for using amulets, scryers, and mirrors to make contact with spirits and angels. Among the objects he used in this way was an obsidian mirror of Aztec origin, now housed in

the British Museum (see www.bl.uk/collection-items/john-dees-spirit-mirror). Dee had contact with other noblemen on the continent when he began his nomadic life in Central Europe. Along with his medium companion Edward Kelley – another occultist, more of a crank, whose performances and claims often pushed the boundaries of Christian tolerance –, he performed divinatory sessions for Emperor Rudolf II (1552-1612); Holy Roman Emperor, King of Bohemia, grandson of Charles V, and therefore a member of the House of Habsburg. It is likely that from these relations, Dee acquired the mirror and perhaps other objects and books from the New World. These may even have included codices such as Codex Laud. According to Burland (1966), Dee should be credited as an owner of Codex Laud at some point in time. Perhaps it was one of the pieces that became scattered after his library was looted at his return from Poland in 1589. But even if this claim cannot be definitively proven, we can be sure that figures devoted to alchemy, astrology, and hermetic knowledge – such as Allen, Dee, Kelley, and Digby – would have recognised the virtues of a manuscript like Codex Laud. Moreover, we can assume that whoever owned this codex would have had some awareness of its oracular capacity.

CONCLUSIONS

I would like to conclude by reiterating and highlighting the main findings of this codicological analysis.

Our observations do not support the idea that the covers were placed on top of painted pages of the codex. Therefore, our study does not lead one to think that the manuscript has missing pages. The covers look to have been attached to the extremes of the strips of this screenfold codex and on the small spaces where the corners were detached there were no traces of gypsum and pigments, nor is there any evidence of matter that could compare physically and visibly to these materials present on other parts of the codex. Instead, there are the remains of a filamentous white-greyish substance. This points to residues of glue, probably coming from orchids or beeswax.

Codex Laud gives the impression of being a well-planned and thoughtful manufactured project. This is shown on the cuts and folds of strips, the strong binding between strips, the careful and neat making of straight lines, the impeccable outlines of figures, the attention payed for covering preparatory lines or sketches, and the relatively few mistakes during the painting-writing stage. It seems also that whoever made the codex was deliberately thinking of its content, planning to have at hand a designed and manufactured document when engaging with calendrical prognostications and prescriptions. Codex Laud, due to its short and small format, was a documents that could be easily transported. And its sober style and unique content makes it a concise and abbreviated book for the expert of the calendar symbolisms.

The codex is made of animal skin in its covers and inner strips. They both went through a special tanning treatment to serve their own purpose, remarkably leaving the covers with the fur of what was likely the head of a jaguar. Leather was then cut to size to obtain three regular strips of the same length. The strips were carefully folded, but if they became weaken or broke during the process they were reinforced with stitching or restored with cross-seams or application of pieces of cloth. Flaps to join strips together were reduced so as to create seamless unions, although these are still perceptible on the reverse. A very effective glue was used to keep these firmly together. Gypsum was afterwards applied with different instruments such as brushes, spatulas, or stone-smoothers, sometimes leaving marks on the codex itself. Nonetheless, some of these marks might be due to the texture and striae of the animal skin.

Gypsum was applied in several layers, which also served the purpose of reinforcing the aforementioned folds. Covers were glued to the extreme ends and a last coat of gypsum was applied, which was burnished to appear smooth and shiny. Then, painting and writing was undertaken. This started with a process of framing the space for chapters with red lines using rulers and precise skill. Afterwards, outlines for the figures and designs were made, using a special tool that had a hard tip, which allowed for a constant flow of ink, but left a fine incision on both sides of the line on the gypsum. The outlines were applied with

abundant ink, which caused some smears and also transfers of stains to the opposite pages. Some figures were then drawn on top of the framing red lines.

Next, colours were applied in layers. This is specially noted in the case of the red colour in Chapter 4 on pages 23 and 24 of the obverse and in the case of the yellow colour in all chapters of the reverse. These noticeable variables are likely due to the application of only a single coat of colour. It seems that colours were applied following a constant order. Red, blue, green, and grey were applied first and then yellow, cream, and orange were last. During the application of these latter, some experimentation is seen especially on the reverse side, since orange and cream were created by applying diluted pigments on top of layers of yellow, similar to a watercolour technique. For some colours, it is clear that they were put on top of black outlines, which means that these were sometimes completed after a first round of colour application.

In Chapter 4 on pages 23-24, the application of colours was not finished. Remarkably, yellow and creams were missing and so do not appear on these pages. On the reverse, the last chapter was also left unfinished. Here, grey was the colour that was mostly missing, along with other designs that were left colourless. There were also some major smears of black ink, which remained uncorrected. Also, on page 22 there was a spill of ink on the figures of offerings, which seems to have delayed and ultimately prevented the application of colours. The precision of tiny, equidistant, regular, and precise lines and dots for the design of furry, feathery, and smokey textures is striking. This is also the case in the depiction of bones, skulls, and bar numbers, although it is likely here that stamps of some kind were used. In general, the manuscript does not contain many mistakes, but smudges and smears are present throughout.

Besides allowing us to note the absence of colours on some chapters, our focus on the matter of colour also led to some further and major revelations. We have argued that colours were thoughtfully applied per chapter, which fits with previous ideas on the matter. Moreover, our identification of colours throughout the codex showed that there are differences of colour shades between chapters. This implies that batches of colour were not applied in a process that extended the stripes and filled up empty spaces. Rather, we contend that colour batches were made specially for each chapter and therefore that the symbolic purposes of each chapter were taken into consideration during the application of colour. In general, red, blue, green, grey, yellow, cream, and orange showed differences between chapters. The case of green was highly remarkable since it was the hue that changed more drastically, at times being more like turquoise and sometimes being more brownish. Thus, our observations of the changing hue of green turned into a good parameter for identifying the changing colour palettes used by the codex's creators. Where green was of a turquoise tonality, it was almost indistinguishable from blue, which is supported by previous spectroscopy results on their similar chemical compositions.

Our analysis of the colours of the codex converged our analysis of the variations of the arrangement of figures on the space of pages. Furthermore, these examinations also connected with different calendric groups depicted throughout the manuscript. My proposal, therefore, is that this codex deals with ten different themes for calendric prognostication and ritual prescription. Nonetheless, the arrangement of spaces within chapters was not perfectly consistent. In addition, there are 3 or even 4 chapters on the reverse that share exactly the same palette of colours. And it must be noted that the criteria of calendric group changes,

unlike colour and notational variability, remains the strongest to make distinctions and point out different chapters of the codex.

Finally, some data that was identified on the materiality of the codex was used to give an account of the biography of this ancient book. On some parts, it is possible to observe stains and globs with an oily look and fuzz sticking to them. They could have originated as a result of someone handling a candle or wax near the codex. This could mean that the codex was used even if it was not yet finished, or still in process of being corrected and re-painted. Tiny pin holes and sunken concavities were also seen, which implies that something may have been leaning on the codex at some point in time. The condition of the gypsum is better preserved on the obverse. The reverse is more damaged, with cracks, detachment of tiny pieces, folds, and bulgy surfaces. Some of this damage may have occurred as the codex was worn out and got dirty by friction. There are also some fingerprints of opaque black ink, probably imprinted by the scribe of the codex since the pages were painted-written.

The *ex libris* stamp looks similar to the style of the 1830s. The covers show holes and paths made by insects, but also striae, which is typical of animal skin. The style and decorative motifs of the slip-case indicates is indicative of a European product from the 16th or 17th century. Noticeably, this slip-case was not bound or sealed with the coat of arms of William Laud and probably travelled with the codex since its arrival to Spain as a kind of protective cover. Lastly, we have proposed that the year of acquisition of this manuscript is 1634 and not 1636 as has been commonly stated. This misunderstanding was probably due to a reading of the catalogues of the Bodleian Library which do not accurately place the codex on the original lists of donations from William Laud. Unfortunately, even if we stipulate that the year of acquisition was 1634 it is still not possible to find out more on the provenance or previous owner of Codex Laud. My assumption is that somebody interested in Hermetica had owned the codex prior to Laud, since it had the legend of “Book of Egyptian Hieroglyphs” on its case. Hermetica was especially praised in occult circles of this epoch, associated with Hermes Trismegistus, who was considered the sage and transmitter of ancient Egyptian knowledge, alchemy, and astrology.

Overall, the main conclusion for our analysis on this magnificent and unique manuscript is that it is a complete codex with no missing pages. However, we do not think that Codex Laud is a finished project; probably kept - and taken to Europe - in the process of being corrected and re-painted. Still, this manuscript of nearly 500 years old and presumably originated from the Tehuacan area of Mesoamerica, raises intriguing questions yet to be investigated.

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